

Challenges as Enablers for High Quality Linked Data: Insights from the Semantic Publishing Challenge

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ABSTRACT

While most challenges organized so far in the Semantic Web domain are focused on comparing tools with respect to different criteria such as their features, competencies, etc., or exploiting semantically enriched data, the Semantic Web Evaluation Challenges series, co-located with the ESWC Semantic Web Conference, aims to compare them based on their output, namely the produced *dataset*. The Semantic Publishing Challenge is one of these challenges. Its goal is to involve participants in extracting data from heterogeneous sources on scholarly publications, and producing Linked Data that can be exploited by the community itself. This paper reviews lessons learned from both (i) the overall organization of the Semantic Publishing Challenge, regarding the definition of the tasks, building the input dataset and forming the evaluation, and (ii) the results produced by the participants, regarding the proposed approaches, the used tools, the preferred vocabularies and the results produced in the three editions of 2014, 2015 and 2016. We compared these lessons to the output of other Semantic Web Evaluation challenges. In this paper, we (i) distill best practices for organizing such challenges that could be applied to similar events, and (ii) report observations on Linked Data publishing derived from the submitted solutions. We conclude that higher quality may be achieved when Linked Data is produced as a result of a challenge, because the competition becomes an incentive, while solutions become better with respect to Linked Data publishing best practices when they are evaluated against the rules of the challenge.

Keywords: Challenge, Semantic Publishing, Linked Data Publishing

1 INTRODUCTION

The Semantic Web aims to extend the human-readable Web by encoding the semantics of resources in a machine-comprehensible and reusable fashion. Over the past years, a growing amount of research on publishing and consuming Linked Data, i.e. data represented and made available in a way that maximizes reusability, has facilitated Semantic Web adoption. However, one of the remaining issues is lack of high-quality Linked Data. A promising means to foster and accelerate the publication of high quality Linked Data is the organization of *challenges*: competitions during which participants complete tasks with innovative solutions that are then ranked in an objective way to determine the winner. A significant number of challenges has been organized so far, including the Semantic Web Challenge¹, its Big Data Track formerly known as the Billion Triples Challenge, and the LinkedUp Challenge², to mention a few of the longest lasting. However, these challenges targeted broad application domains and were more focused on innovative ways of exploiting Semantic Web enabled tools (*Linked Data consumption*) than on the output actually produced (*Linked Data production*). Therefore, such challenges enable advancement of Semantic Web technology but overlook the possibility of also advancing Linked Datasets per se.

This paper focuses on a series of Challenges in the Semantic Publishing domain. *Semantic publishing* is defined as “the enhancement of scholarly publications by the use of modern Web standards to improve interactivity, openness and usability, including the use of ontologies to encode rich semantics in the form

46 of machine-readable RDF metadata” by ?. The first Semantic Publishing Challenge, of 2014, was themed
47 “Assessing the Quality of Scientific Output” (?)³, in 2015 we mentioned the techniques more explicitly by
48 appending “. . . by Information Extraction and Interlinking” (?)⁴, and in 2016 we generalized to “. . . in
49 its Ecosystem” to emphasize the multiple dimensions of scientific quality and the great potential impact
50 of producing Linked Data about it (?)⁵.

51 According to ?, extracting, annotating and sharing scientific data (by which, here, we mean standalone
52 research datasets, data inside documents, as well as metadata about datasets and documents) and then
53 building new research efforts on them, can lead to a data value chain producing value for the scholar
54 and Semantic Web community. On the one hand, the scholar community benefits from a challenge that
55 produces data, as the challenge results in more data and in data of higher quality being available to the
56 community to exploit. On the other hand, the Semantic Web community benefits: participants optimize
57 their tools towards performance in this particular challenge, but such optimisations may also improve the
58 tools in general. Once such tools are reused, any other dataset benefits from their advancements, because
59 the processes producing them has been improved. However, bootstrapping and enabling such value chains
60 is not easy.

61 In a recent publication (?), we discussed lessons we learned from our experience in organizing the
62 first two editions of the Semantic Publishing Challenge – mainly from the perspective of how to improve
63 the organization of further editions and of providing a better service to the scholar community. The
64 lessons are related to the challenge organization, namely defining the tasks, building the input datasets
65 and performing the evaluation, as well as lessons we learned by studying the solutions, with respect to the
66 methodologies, tools and ontologies used, and data produced by the participants. We organized the third
67 edition based on these lessons learned.

68 In this paper, we revise our lessons learned, taking into consideration experience gained by organizing
69 the challenge’s third edition, whose results validate in principle our lessons learned. We argue that
70 challenges may act as enablers for the generation of higher quality Linked Data, because of the competitive
71 aspect. However, organizing a successful challenge is not an easy task. Therefore, the goal of this paper is
72 to distill *generic best practices*, which could be applied to similar events, rendering the challenge tasks into
73 meaningful milestones for efficient Linked Data generation and publishing. To achieve that, we validated
74 the generalizability of our lessons learned against the other Semantic Web Evaluation Challenges^{6,7,8}.

75 We concluded that our lessons learned are applicable to other challenges too; thus they can be
76 considered *best practices* for organizing a challenge. Other challenge organizers may benefit from relying
77 on these best practices when organizing their own challenge. Additionally, we thoroughly analyze and
78 report best practices followed by the Linked Data that the *solutions* to our challenge’s tasks produce. Our
79 study of the different solutions provides insights regarding different approaches that address the same
80 task, namely it acts as if the challenge benchmarks those different solutions against a common problem.

81 Thus, besides the scholarly community and the CEUR-WS.org open access repository, which is the
82 owner of the underlying data, the broader Linked Data community may benefit from looking into our
83 cumulative results. Other Linked Data owners may find details on different approaches dealing with the
84 same problem and the corresponding results they produce. Taking them into consideration, they can
85 determine their own approach for an equivalent case or even consider launching a corresponding challenge
86 to determine the best performing tool with respect to the desired results and consider this one for their
87 regular long term use. Moreover, other Linked Data publishers may advise the results or consider the best
88 practices as their guidelines for improving their tools and thus their results.

89 In summary, our contributions are:

- 90 • an *outline of challenges* organized in the field of Linked Data and Semantic Web technologies,
- 91 • an *exhaustive analysis* of all solutions to every task of all editions of the Semantic Publishing
92 Challenge series,
- 93 • a *systematic discussion of lessons* that we have learned from organizing the Semantic Publishing
94 Challenge, and
- 95 • a structured set of *best practices* for organizing similar challenges, resulting from validating our
96 lessons against other Semantic Web Evaluation challenges.

97 The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews related work; in particular it
98 sets the background for our study by recapitulating the Semantic Publishing Challenges run so far and

99 comparing them to related challenges. Section 3 revisits the lessons learned, taking into consideration all
100 three editions, validates them against other challenges and concludes in best practices for organizing such
101 challenges. Section 4 exhaustively and cumulatively analyses the submitted solutions to all tasks of all
102 challenge series and Section 6 summarizes our conclusions.

103 **2 BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK**

104 This section sets the background of the Semantic Publishing Challenges so far. To this end, it first discusses
105 work that is related to different aspects, i.e. other reviews of challenge series (??), and quality assessment
106 as an alternative way of generating high quality Linked Data (??). Section 2.1 then summarizes other
107 challenges in the Semantic Web community. Last, Section 2.2 recapitulates the Semantic Publishing
108 Challenges run so far, including the definitions of their tasks, and their outcomes.

109 **2.1 State of the Art on Previously Organized Challenges**

110 Several related challenges were organized in the past for different purposes and application domains. In
111 this section, we summarize the most well-known and most closely related challenges in the Semantic Web
112 field with the longest duration.

113 **2.1.1 Ontology Matching Challenges**

114 The *Ontology Matching Challenges*⁹ have been organized since 2004 by the Ontology Alignment Evaluation
115 Initiative (OAEI)¹⁰ and co-located with several top Information Systems and Web conferences such
116 as WWW¹¹ or VLDB¹². It aims to forge a consensus for evaluating the different emerging methods for
117 schema or ontology matching. The OAEI goals are to assess the strengths and weaknesses of alignment/
118 matching systems, compare the performance of techniques, and improve evaluation techniques to help
119 improving the work on ontology alignment/matching through evaluating the techniques' performances.
120 Following a similar structure as the Semantic Publishing Challenge, the OAEI challenge provides a list
121 of test ontologies as training datasets. The SEALS infrastructure to evaluate the results has been made
122 available since 2011. The results are presented during the Ontology Matching workshop, which is usually
123 co-located with the International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC). The tests and results of the challenge
124 are published for further analysis.

125 **2.1.2 Semantic Web Challenge**

126 The *Semantic Web Challenge*¹³ aims to apply Semantic Web techniques in building online end-user
127 applications that integrate, combine and deduce information needed to assist users in performing tasks. It
128 features a track about Big Data designed to demonstrate approaches which can work on Web scale using
129 realistic Web-quality data. The Big Data Track, formerly known as the *Billion Triples Challenge (BTC)*,
130 started from 2008 mostly co-located with ISWC¹⁴. The Billion Triples Challenge aimed to demonstrate
131 the capability of Semantic Web technologies to process very large and messy data as typically found on
132 the Web. The track was renamed to "Big Data Track" because very large data sets are now ubiquitous
133 and the competition was opened to broader range of researchers dealing with their own big data. The
134 functionality of submitted solutions is open but, to address real scalability issues, it forces all participants
135 to use a specific Billion Triple Challenge Dataset provided by the challenge's organizers.

136 **2.1.3 Question Answering over Linked Data (QALD)**

137 The *Question Answering over Linked Data (QALD)* challenge¹⁵ (??) focuses on answering natural
138 language or keyword-based questions over linked datasets. Co-located with the ESWC Semantic Web
139 Conference in its first two editions in 2011 and 2013, it moved to the Conference and Labs of the
140 Evaluation Forum (CLEF) for the three following editions, to return to ESWC as a part of its Semantic
141 Web Evaluation Challenges track explained below. In all editions, a set of up to 340 questions over
142 DBpedia¹⁶ served as input; participants were expected to answer these questions. The 2013 to 2016
143 editions had a task on multilingual questions, while from 2014, a task on hybrid question answering over
144 RDF and free text was added. Some editions considered alternative datasets, e.g., about drugs or music,
145 and had alternative sub-tasks on answering questions over interlinked datasets or finding lexicalizations of
146 ontological terms. Among the submitted solutions, only few address the question/answering issues over a
147 distributed and large collection of interconnected datasets.

148 The first two editions of QALD Challenge were reviewed (?) similarly to our work and "discuss how
149 the second evaluation addressed some of the issues and limitations which arose from the first one, as

150 well as the open issues to be addressed in future competitions”. Like us, they present the definition of
151 the QALD challenge’s tasks and the datasets used, and draw conclusions for the subsequent evaluation
152 of question answering systems from reviewing concrete results of the first two challenge editions. *Their*
153 review of related work includes a review of methods for evaluating question answering systems, whereas
154 the Semantic Publishing Challenge was created to address the lack of such methods for evaluating
155 semantic publishing tools (cf. Section 2.2). In relation to our presentation of lessons learned for challenge
156 organization (Section 3) and lessons learned about semantic publishing tools (Section 4), which, together,
157 constitute the main contribution of this paper, their conclusions are limited.

158 **2.1.4 LAK Challenges**

159 The *LAK Challenges*¹⁷ use a specific dataset of structured metadata from research publications in the field
160 of learning analytics. The challenge was organized in 2011 for the first time and has so far continued
161 yearly with the LAK conference. Beyond merely publishing the data, the LAK challenges encourage its
162 innovative use and exploitation. Participants submit a meaningful use case of the dataset in the scope of
163 six topic categories, such as comparison of the LAK and EDM (Educational Data Mining) communities,
164 innovative applications to explore, navigate and visualize, enrichment of the Dataset, and usage of the
165 dataset in recommender systems. Considering that a lot of information is still available only in textual
166 form, the submitted approaches can not only deal with the specific character of structured data. The aim
167 for further challenges is to combine solutions for processing both structured and unstructured information
168 from distributed datasets.

169 **2.1.5 LinkedUp**

170 The *LinkedUp* challenge¹⁸ was run by the LinkedUp project¹⁹ since 2014. The main purpose of the
171 project was to push educational organizations to make their data publicly available on the Web. One of
172 the activities towards this purpose was to organize the *LinkedUp Challenge*²⁰. The three editions of the
173 challenge focused on three different levels of maturity: demo prototypes and applications, innovative
174 tools and applications, and mature data-driven applications. Participants were asked to submit demos of
175 tools that analyze and/or integrate open Web data for educational purposes. For all the above challenges,
176 the participants were asked to submit a scientific paper along with their tool and dataset.

177 ? present lessons learned from the LinkedUp project (Linking Web Data for Education). Nevertheless,
178 their paper provides a summary of the outcomes of the project, including a summary of the LinkedUp
179 Challenge, rather than a systematically structured account of lessons learned.

180 **2.1.6 Dialog State Tracking Challenge (DSTC)**

181 The challenge series review that is most closely related to ours in its methodology has been carried out by
182 ? over a challenge series from an unrelated field of computer science: the Dialog State Tracking Challenge
183 (DSTC) on “correctly inferring the state of [a] conversation [...] given all of the dialog history”. Like our
184 review it is based on three editions of a challenge, each of which built on its predecessor’s results, and it
185 presents the definition of the challenge’s tasks and the datasets used. Like we do in Section 4, they provide
186 a structured overview of the submissions to the DSTC challenges. However, the focus of their review is
187 on the evolution of tools in their domain of dialog state tracking, whereas our review additionally covers
188 lessons learned for challenge design (cf. Section 3).

189 **2.1.7 Other related works**

190 There are further related works and challenges that we consider out of the scope of our work, as they
191 are not focused on linked datasets. For example, the *AI Mashup Challenge*²¹ as a part of the ESWC
192 conference focused on innovative mashups, i.e. web applications combining multiple services and datasets,
193 that were evaluated by a jury. Information Retrieval campaigns are a series of comparative evaluation
194 methods that originate from 1960s and are used to compare various retrieval strategies or systems. As an
195 example of such compains SemEval (Semantic Evaluation)²² is one of the ongoing series of evaluations
196 of computational semantic analysis systems with the focus of Textual Similarity and Question Answering
197 and Sentiment Analysis?. The *Computational Linguistics Scientific Document Summarization Shared*
198 *Task (CL-SciSumm)*²³ is based on a corpus of annotated documents; tasks focus on correctly identifying
199 the underlying text that a summary refers to, but also on generating summaries.

200 **2.1.8 Semantic Web Evaluation Challenges**

201 The *Semantic Web Evaluation Challenges*^{24,25,26}, including our Semantic Publishing Challenge, aim at
202 developing a set of common benchmarks and establish evaluation procedures, tasks and datasets in the

Table 1. Semantic Web Evaluation Challenges

Abbreviation	Challenge	Years
SemPub	Semantic Publishing Challenge	2014, 2015, 2016
CLSA	(Concept-Level) Sentiment Analysis Challenge	2014, 2015, 2016
RecSys	Linked Open Data-Enabled Recommender System Challenge	2014, 2015
OKE	Open Knowledge Extraction Challenge	2015, 2016
SAQ	Schema-agnostic Queries over Linked Data	2015
QALD	Open Challenge on Question Answering over Linked Data	2016
Top-K	Top-K Shortest Path in Large Typed RDF Graphs Challenge	2016

203 Semantic Web field. They are organized as an official track of ESWC, which introduces common standards
 204 for its challenges, e.g., common deadlines for the publication of the training and evaluation datasets. The
 205 purpose of the challenges is to showcase methods and tools on tasks common to the Semantic Web and
 206 adjacent disciplines, in a controlled setting involving rigorous evaluation.

207 **Concept-Level Sentiment Analysis Challenge** The *Concept-Level Sentiment Analysis Challenge*
 208 (*CLSA*) focuses on semantics as a key factor for sentiment detection rather than only lexical analysis of
 209 text, ? and ?. Participants are asked to use Semantic Web technology to improve their sentiment analysis
 210 system and measure the performance of the system²⁷ within the Sentiment Analysis track of SEMEVAL
 211 2015 workshop²⁸. An automatic evaluation tool²⁹ was applied to the submissions; it was made available
 212 to the participants before their submission. In the second edition, participants were asked to submit a
 213 concept-level opinion-mining engine that exploited linked datasets such as DBpedia.

214 **Linked Open Data-Enabled Recommender Systems Challenge** The *Linked Open Data-Enabled*
 215 *Recommender Systems Challenge* ? was designed with two main goals: i) establish links between the two
 216 communities of recommendation systems and Semantic Web, ii) develop content-based recommendation
 217 systems using semantic web and interlinking technologies. The first edition featured three independent
 218 tasks related to a book recommendation use case. While the first edition was successful, the second
 219 edition was cancelled because it had no participants.

220 **Open Knowledge Extraction Challenge** The *Open Knowledge Extraction Challenge (OKE)* focuses
 221 on content extraction from textual data using Linked Data technology, ?. The challenge was divided
 222 into two sub-tasks³⁰ focusing on entity recognition and entity typing. The participants of the challenge
 223 were the developers of four different well-known system in this community. The three defined tasks
 224 were focused on a) entity recognition, linking and typing for knowledge base population, b) entity typing
 225 for vocabulary and knowledge Base enrichment and c) Web-scale knowledge extraction by exploiting
 226 structured annotation. The submissions were evaluated using two different methods: i) using datasets
 227 for training purposes and for evaluating the performance of the submitted approaches, ii) establishing
 228 an evaluation framework to measure the accuracy of the systems. The applications of task 1 and 2 were
 229 published as web services with input/output provided in the NLP Interchange Format³¹.

230 **Schema-Agnostic Queries over Linked Data Challenge** The *Schema-Agnostic Queries over Linked*
 231 *Data Challenge (SAQ)* was designed to invite schema-agnostic query approaches and systems ?. The goal
 232 of this challenge is to improve querying approaches over complex databases with large schemata and
 233 to relieve users from the need to understand the database schema. Tasks were defined for two types of
 234 queries: schema-agnostic SPARQL queries and schema-agnostic keyword-based queries. Participants
 235 were asked to submit the results together with their approach without changing the query syntax but with
 236 different vocabularies and structural changes. A gold standard dataset was used to measure precision,
 237 recall and F1-score.

2.2 Semantic Publishing Challenge: 2014–2016

In this section, we briefly summarize the Semantic Publishing Challenge history to provide the necessary background for the following discussion. More detailed reports have been published separately by [1], [2], and [3].

We sought a way to challenge the semantic publishing community to accomplish tasks whose results could be compared in an objective way. After some preliminary discussion, we focused on information extraction tasks. The basic idea was to provide as input some scholarly papers — in multiple formats — and some queries in natural language. Participants were asked to extract data from these papers and to publish them as an RDF dataset, that could be used to answer the input queries. The best performing approach was identified automatically by comparing the output of the queries in the produced datasets against a gold standard, and by measuring precision and recall. Our selection of queries was motivated by quality assessment scenarios: how can the extracted information serve as indicators for the quality of scientific output such as publications or events. The same motivation, structure and evaluation procedure have been maintained in the following years, with some improvements and extensions.

All challenge’s series’ tasks (Section 2.2.1), the input to the tasks, namely the training and evaluation datasets (Section 2.2.2), the output, namely the submitted solutions and the produced dataset (Section 2.2.3) and how their evaluation was conducted (Section 2.2.4) are briefly explained below.

2.2.1 Tasks Evolution

Table 2 summarizes the tasks’ full history. For each year and each task, we highlight the data source and the format of the input files, along with a short description of the task and a summary on the participation.

2014 edition tasks. The first edition had two main tasks (Task 1 and Task 2) and an open task (Task 3, see [1] for full details and statistics of this challenge’s edition).

For Task 1, the participants were asked to extract information from selected CEUR-WS.org workshop proceedings volumes to enable the computation of indicators for the workshops’ quality assessment. The input files were HTML tables of content using different levels of semantic markup, as well as PDF full text. The participants were asked to answer twenty different queries.

For Task 2, the input dataset included XML-encoded research papers, derived from the PubMedCentral and Pensoft Open Access archives. The participants were asked to extract data about citations to assess the value of articles, for instance by considering citations’ position in the paper, their co-location with other citations or their purpose. In total, they were asked to answer ten different queries. Dataset and queries were completely disjoint from Task 1.

Having called for submissions, we received feedback from the community that mere information extraction, even if motivated by certain assessment, was not the most exciting task related to the future of scholarly publishing, as it assumed a traditional publishing model. Furthermore, to address the challenge’s primary target, i.e. ‘publishing’ rather than just ‘metadata extraction’, we widened the scope by adding an open task (Task 3). Participants were asked to showcase data-driven applications that would eventually support publishing. We received a good number of submissions; winners were selected by a jury.

2015 edition tasks. In 2015 we were asked to include only tasks that could be evaluated in a fully objective manner, and thus we discarded the 2014’s edition open task (Task 3).

While Task 1 queries remained largely stable from 2014 to 2015, the queries for Task 2 changed. We transformed Task 2 into a PDF mining task and thus moved all PDF-related queries there. The rationale was to differentiate tasks on the basis of the competencies and tools required to solve them. Since the input format was completely new and we expected different teams to participate (as actually happened) we wanted to explore new areas and potentially interesting information. In fact, we asked participants to extract data not only on citations but also on affiliations and fundings. The number of queries remained unchanged (ten in total). We also decided to use the same source for both tasks, and to make them interplay. CEUR-WS.org data has become the central focus of the whole Challenge, for two reasons: on the one hand, the data provider (CEUR-WS.org) takes advantage of a broader community that builds on its data, which, before the Semantic Publishing Challenges, had not been available as Linked Data³². On the other hand, data consumers gain the opportunity to assess the quality of scientific venues by taking a deeper look into their history, as well as the quality of the publications.

In 2015, we also introduced a new Task 3. Instead of being an open task, Task 3 was focused on interlinking the dataset produced by the winners of Task 1 from the previous edition of the Semantic Publishing Challenge with other datasets in the Linked Data cloud.

292 **2016 edition tasks.** The tasks of 2016 edition were designed to ensure continuity and to allow previous
293 participants to use and refine their tools.

294 In particular, Task 1 was unchanged except for some minor details on queries. Task 2 was still on
295 PDF information extraction but queries were slightly changed: considering the interest and results of the
296 participants in the past, we did not include citations any more. Rather, we added some queries on the
297 identification of the structural components of the papers (table of contents, captions, figures and tables)
298 and maintained queries on funding agencies and projects. In total, we had ten queries in 2016 as well.

299 Task 3 remained the same but it was repurposed. Instead of only aiming for cross-dataset links
300 between the dataset produced by Task 1 winners of the 2014 edition and other external datasets, Task 3
301 was also focused on interlinking the datasets produced by the winners of Task 1 and Task 2 of the 2015
302 edition. Thus, the task aimed not only for *cross-dataset* but also for *cross-task* links: the goal was to
303 link entities identified in the CEUR-WS.org website with the same entities that were extracted from the
304 proceedings papers. Moreover, the number of external datasets was reduced.

305 **2.2.2 Input: Training and Evaluation Datasets**

306 In this section we give an overview of the datasets used for the above mentioned tasks. These datasets in
307 fact were incrementally refined and, as we will discuss later, some valuable indications can be taken from
308 their analysis. For each task, and for each year, we published two datasets: (i) a training dataset (TD) on
309 which the participants could test and train their extraction tools and (ii) an evaluation dataset (ED) made
310 available a few days before the final submission and used as input for the final evaluation.

311 **Training and Evaluation dataset for Task 1.** The CEUR-WS.org workshop proceedings volumes
312 served as the source for selecting the training and evaluation datasets of Task 1 in all challenge editions.
313 In this data source, which spanned data from 20 years, workshop proceedings volumes were represented
314 in different formats and at different levels of encoding quality and semantics. An HTML 4 main index
315 page³³ links to all workshop proceedings volumes, which have HTML tables of contents and contain
316 PDF or PostScript full texts. A mixture of different HTML formats (no semantic markup at all, different
317 versions of microformats, RDFa) were chosen for both the training and evaluation datasets. The training
318 dataset comprised all volumes of several workshop series, including, e.g., Linked Data on the Web, and
319 all workshops of some conferences, e.g., of several editions of ESWC. In 2014 and 2015, the evaluation
320 dataset was created by adding further workshops on top of the training dataset. To support the evolution
321 of extraction tools, the training datasets of 2015 and 2016 were based on the unions of the training and
322 evaluation datasets of the previous years. In 2015 and 2016, the Task 1 dataset of the previous year served
323 as an input to Task 3.

324 **Training and Evaluation dataset for Task 2.** In 2014, the datasets for Task 2 included XML files
325 encoded in JATS³⁴ and TaxPub, an official extension of JATS customized for taxonomic treatments³⁵.
326 The training dataset consisted of 150 files from 15 journals, while the evaluation dataset included 400
327 papers and was a superset of the training dataset. In 2015, we switched to PDF information extraction:
328 the training dataset included 100 papers taken from some of the workshops analyzed in Task 1, while the
329 evaluation dataset included 200 papers taken from randomly selected workshops (uniform to the training
330 dataset). In 2016 we reduced the number of papers increasing the cases for each query. Thus, we included
331 50 PDF papers in the training dataset and 40 in the evaluation dataset. Again, the papers in these two sets
332 were distributed in the same way and used different styles for headers, acknowledgments and structural
333 components.

334 **Training and Evaluation dataset for Task 3.** The training dataset for Task 3 consists of the CEUR-
335 WS.org dataset produced by the 2014 winning tool of Task 1³⁶, COLINDA³⁷, DBLP³⁸, Lancet³⁹, SWDF⁴⁰,
336 and Springer LD⁴¹ in 2015 and the CEUR-WS.org datasets produced by the 2015 winning tools of Task
337 1⁴² and Task 2⁴³, of COLINDA, DBLP, and Springer LD in 2016.

338 **2.2.3 Output: Solutions and Datasets produced**

339 There were four distinct solutions in total for Task 1 during the three editions of the challenge, eight
340 distinct solutions in total for Task 2 and none for Task 3 during the last two editions. All solutions for
341 each task are briefly summarized here.

342 **Task 1.** There were four distinct solutions proposed to address Task 1 in 2014 and 2015 editions of
343 the challenge. Three participated in both editions, whereas the fourth solution participated only in the

344 2015 edition. All solutions are briefly introduced here and summarized in Table 3, Table 7, Table 10,
345 Table 8 and Table 9. Table 3 provides details about the methodologies, approach and implementation each
346 solution followed. Table 7 summarizes the model and vocabularies/ontologies each solution used (both
347 for Task 1 and Task 2), whereas Table 10 provides statistics regarding the dataset schema/entities and
348 triples/size each solution produced (again both for Task 1 and Task 2). Last, Table 8 summarizes the data
349 model each solution considered and Table 9 the number of instances extracted and annotated per concept
350 for each solution.

351 **Solution 1.1** ? and ? presented a case-specific crawling based approach for addressing Task 1. It
352 relies on an extensible template-dependent crawler that uses sets of special predefined templates based on
353 XPath and regular expressions to extract the content from HTML and convert it in RDF. The RDF is then
354 processed to merge resources using fuzzy-matching. The use of the crawler turns the system tolerant to
355 invalid HTML pages. This solution improved its precision in 2015 as well the richness of the data model.

356 **Solution 1.2** ? and ? exploited a generic tool for generating RDF data from heterogeneous data. It uses
357 the RDF Mapping Language (RML)⁴⁴ to define how data extracted from CEUR-WS Web pages should
358 be semantically annotated. RML extends R2RML⁴⁵ to express mapping rules from heterogeneous data to
359 RDF. CSS3 selectors⁴⁶ are considered to extract the data from the HTML pages. The RML mapping rules
360 are parsed and executed by the RML Processor⁴⁷. In 2015 the solution reconsidered its data model and
361 was extended to validate both the mapping documents and the final RDF, resulting in an overall improved
362 quality dataset.

363 **Solution 1.3** ? and ? designed a case-specific solution that relies on chunk-based and sentence-based
364 Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifiers which are exploited to semantically characterize parts of
365 CEUR-WS proceedings textual contents. Thanks to a pipeline of text analysis components based on the
366 GATE Text Engineering Framework⁴⁸, each HTML page is characterized by structural and linguistic
367 features: these features are then exploited to train the classifiers on the ground-truth provided by the
368 subset of CEUR-WS proceedings with microformat annotations. A heuristic-based annotation sanitizer is
369 applied to fix classifiers imperfections and interlink annotations. The produced dataset is also extended
370 with information retrieved from external resources.

371 **Solution 1.4** ? presented an application of the FITLayout framework⁴⁹. This solution participated in
372 the Semantic Publishing Challenge only in 2015. It combines different page analysis methods, i.e. layout
373 analysis and visual and textual feature classification to analyze the rendered pages, rather than their code.
374 The solution is quite generic but needs to be domain/case-specific at certain phases (model building step).

375 **Task 2** There were eight distinct solutions proposed to address Task 2 in the 2015 and 2016 editions
376 of the challenge. Three participated in both editions, three only in 2015 and two only in 2016. As the
377 definition of Task 2 changed fundamentally from 2014 to 2015, the only solution submitted for Task
378 2 in 2014 ? is not comparable to the 2015 and 2016 solutions and therefore not discussed here. All
379 solutions for Task 2 – except for the one of 2014 – are briefly introduced here and summarized in Table 6,
380 Table 7 and Table 11. Table 4 and Table 5 provides details about the methodologies and approach each
381 solution followed. Table 6 summarizes details regarding the implementation and its components each
382 solution developed to address Task 2. Table 7 summarizes the model and vocabularies/ontologies each
383 solution used (both for Task 1 and Task 2), whereas Table 11 provides statistics regarding the dataset
384 schema/entities and triples/size each solution produced (again both for Task 1 and Task 2).

385 **Solution 2.1** ? relied on CERMINE⁵⁰, an open source system for extracting structured metadata and
386 references from scientific publications published as PDF files. It has a loosely captured architecture and a
387 modular workflow based on supervised and unsupervised machine-learning techniques, which simplifies
388 the system's adaptation to new document layouts and styles. It employs an enhanced Docstrum algorithm
389 for page segmentation to obtain the document's hierarchical structure, Support Vector Machines (SVM)
390 to classify its zones, heuristics and regular expressions for individual and Conditional Random Fields (CRF)
391 for affiliation parsing and thus to identify organization, address and country in affiliation. Last, K-Means
392 clustering was used for reference extraction to divide references zones into individual reference strings.

393 **Solution 2.2** ?? implemented a processing pipeline that analyzes a PDF document structure incorporat-
394 ing a diverse set of machine learning techniques. To be more precise, they employ unsupervised machine
395 learning techniques (Merge-&-Split algorithm) to extract text blocks and supervised (Max Entropy and

396 Beam search) to extend the document's structure analysis and identify sections and captions. They
397 combine the above with clustering techniques to obtain the article's hierarchical table of content and
398 classify blocks into different meta-data categories. Heuristics are applied to detect the reference section
399 and sequence classification to categorize the tokens of individual references to strings. Last, Named Entity
400 Recognition (NER) is used to extract references to grants, funding agencies, projects, figure and table
401 captions.

402 **Solution 2.3** ?? relied on the Metadata And Citations Jailbreaker (MACJa – IPA) in 2015, which was
403 extended to the Article Content Miner (ACM) in 2016. The tool integrates hybrid techniques based
404 on Natural Language Processing (NLP, Combinatory Categorical Grammar, Discourse Representation
405 Theory, Linguistic Frames), Discourse Reference Extraction and Linking, and Topic Extraction. It also
406 employs heuristics to exploit existing lexical resources and gazetteers to generate representation structures.
407 Moreover, it incorporates FRED⁵¹, a novel machine reader and includes modules to query external
408 services to enhance and validate data.

409 **Solution 2.4** ?? relying on LODeXporter⁵², proposed an iterative rule-based pattern matching approach.
410 The system is composed by two modules: (i) a text mining pipeline based on GATE framework to
411 extract structural and semantic entities. It leverages existing NER-based text mining tools to extract both
412 structural and semantic elements, employing post-processing heuristics to detect or correct the authors
413 affiliations in a fuzzy manner, and (ii) a LOD exporter, to translate the document annotations into RDF
414 according to custom rules.

415 **Solution 2.5** ? relies on a rule-based and pattern matching approach, implemented in Python. Some
416 external services are employed for improving the quality of the results (for instance, DBLP for validating
417 author's data), as well as regular expressions, NLP methods and heuristics for HTML document style and
418 standard bibliographic description. It also relies on an external tools to extract the plain text from PDFs.

419 **Solution 2.6** ? extended their framework used for Task 1 (and indicated as Solution 1.3 before) to extract
420 data from PDF as well. Their linear pipeline includes text processing and entity recognition modules. It
421 employs external services for mining PDF articles and heuristics to validate, refine, sanitize and normalize
422 the data. Moreover, linguistic and structural analysis based on chunk-based & sentence-based SVM
423 classifiers are employed, as well as enrichment by linking with external resources such as Bibsonomy,
424 DBpedia spotlight, DBLP, CrossRef, FundRef & FreeCite.

425 **Solution 2.7** ? proposed a heuristic-based approach that uses a combination of tag-/rule-based and plain
426 text information extraction techniques combined with generic heuristics and patterns (regular expressions).
427 Their approach identifies patterns and rules from integrated formats.

428 **Solution 2.8** ? proposed a solution based on a sequential three-level Conditional Random Fields (CRF)
429 supervised learning approach. Their approach follows the same feature list as ?. However, they extract
430 PDF to an XML that conforms to the NLM JATS DTD, and generate RDF using an XSLT transformation
431 tool dedicated for JATS.

432 **2.2.4 Tasks Evaluation**

433 The evaluation of the submitted solutions was conducted in a transparent and objective way by measuring
434 precision and recall. To perform the evaluation, we relied on (i) a gold standard and (ii) an evaluation tool
435 which was developed to automate the procedure.

436 **Gold standard** The gold standard used for each task's evaluation was generated *manually*. It consisted
437 of a set of CSV files, each corresponding to the output of one of the queries used for the evaluation.
438 Each file was built after checking the original sources — for instance HTML proceedings in case of
439 Task 1 and PDF papers for Task 2 — and looking for the output of the corresponding query; then, it
440 was double-checked by the organizers. Furthermore, we also made available the gold standard to the
441 participants (after their submission) so as they have the chance to report inaccuracies or inconsistencies.
442 The final manually-checked version of the CSV files was used as input for the evaluation tool.

443 **Evaluation tool** The evaluation tool⁵³ compares the output of the queries provided by the participants
444 (in CSV) against the gold standard and measures precision and recall. It was not made available to the
445 participants after the 2014 edition, it was only made available after the 2015 edition, while it was made

446 available already by the end of the training for the 2016 edition. This not only increased transparency but
447 also allowed participants to refine their tools and address output imperfections, increasing this way the
448 quality of their results.

449 **3 BEST PRACTICES FOR CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION**

450 In this section we discuss lessons learned from our experience in organizing the challenge and from
451 (even unexpected) aspects that emerged while running the challenge. This section presents the lessons
452 learned by looking at the solutions and data produced by the participants. We have grouped the lessons in
453 categories for clarity, even though there is some overlap between them.

454 Moreover, we validated our lessons learned with respect to other Semantic Web Evaluation Challenges,
455 aiming to assess whether the lessons learned from the Semantic Publishing Challenge are transferable to
456 their settings too. Besides the Semantic Publishing Challenge, another five challenges are organized in
457 the frame of the Semantic Web Evaluation Challenges track at the ESWC Semantic Web Conference (cf.
458 Section 2.1). To validate our challenge's lessons learned, we conducted a survey, which we circulated
459 among the challenge organizers of the different Semantic Web Evaluation Challenges. One organizer
460 per challenge filled in the questionnaire, providing representative answers for the respective challenge.
461 Based on our survey's results, we distill generic best practices that could be applied to similar events. Our
462 lessons learned are outlined in this section, together with their validation based on the other challenges, as
463 well as the corresponding distilled best practices.

464 **3.1 Lessons learned from defining tasks**

465 For the Semantic Publishing Challenge, it was difficult to define appealing tasks that bridge the gap
466 between building up initial datasets and exploring possibilities for innovative semantic publishing. There-
467 fore, as discussed in Section 2.2, we refined the tasks over the years according to the participants' and
468 organizers' feedback.

469 **3.1.1 Task continuity**

470 **Lesson:** In the case of the Semantic Publishing Challenge, the first edition's tasks were well-perceived
471 by potential participants and all of them had submissions. In the second edition (2015), in fact, the
472 challenge was re-organized aiming to commit participants to re-submit overall improved versions of
473 their first edition's submissions. Results were positive, as the majority of the participants of the first
474 edition competed in the second one too. Therefore, task continuity is a key aspect of the Semantic
475 Publishing Challenge, whose tasks in every year are broadly the same as the previous year's edition,
476 allowing participants to reuse their tools to adapt to the new call after some tuning.

477 **Validation:** According to the results of our survey, three of the other four Semantic Web Evaluation
478 challenges have also been organized for several times. Table 1 shows the sustainability of the challenges
479 considering recency and regularity of revisions over their lifetime. Task continuity was embraced in all
480 challenges by their participants, who not only resubmitted their solutions but also showed continuously
481 improved performance for all three challenges that had multiple editions, according to the organizers
482 answers to our survey.

483 **Best Practice:** Tasks should be continued over the course of different editions. Nevertheless, they
484 should be adjusted to pose new challenges that allow the authors of previous editions' submissions
485 to participate again in the challenge, thus offering them incentives to improve their solution, without
486 excluding though new submissions at the same time.

487 **3.1.2 Distinct Tasks**

488 **Lesson:** The initial goal of the Semantic Publishing Challenge was to explore a larger amount of
489 information derived from CEUR-WS.org data and to offer a broad spectrum of alternative options for
490 potential participants but, in retrospect, such heterogeneity proved to become a limitation. One of the
491 main problems we faced was that some of the queries classified under the same task were cumbersome
492 for the participants. For instance, in particular the submissions to Task 2 – extraction from XML and
493 PDF – showed an unexpectedly low performance. The main reason, in our opinion, is that the task was
494 actually composed of two sub-tasks that required different tools and technologies: some queries required
495 participants to basically map data from XML/PDF to RDF, while the others required additional processing

496 of the content. Potential participants were discouraged to participate as they only felt competitive for
497 the one and not for the other. A sharper distinction between tasks would have been more appropriate.
498 In particular, it is important to separate tasks on plain data extraction from those on natural language
499 processing and semantic analysis.

500 **Validation:** Based on the results of our survey, the Semantic Web Evaluation challenges were designed
501 with more than one task, more precisely, on average three tasks per challenge. In addition, all the
502 individual tasks of the challenges were defined related to each other but independently at the same time,
503 so that participants could take part in all or some of the tasks. Nevertheless, only two challenges had
504 submissions for all tasks, while three out of the five challenges lacked submissions only for one task.
505 All challenges though, according to our survey, split the tasks considering the required competencies
506 to accomplish them. Three out of the five challenges even distinguish the training dataset used by each
507 task to render the different tasks even more distinct. This contributes to enabling participation on certain
508 tasks, while more challenging tasks or tasks of different nature are isolated. Thus, participants are not
509 discouraged from participating if they are not competent for these parts to participate in the challenge for
510 tasks they are.

511 **Best Practice:** Splitting tasks with a clear and sharp distinction of the competencies required to
512 accomplish them is a success key factor. Task should be defined taking into consideration the technology,
513 tools and skills required to accomplish them.

514 **3.1.3 Participants involvement**

515 **Lesson:** One of the incentives of the challenge's successive editions was to involve participants in the
516 tasks' definition, because potential tasks or obstacles might be easier, if not intuitive, to be identified by
517 them. However, even though we collected feedback from previous years' participants when designing the
518 tasks, we noticed that such a preliminary phase was not given enough attention. Even though participants
519 provided feedback immediately after the challenge was completed they were not equally eager to give
520 feedback when they were asked just before the new edition was launched. Talking to participants, in fact,
521 helped us to identify alternative tasks.

522 **Validation:** It appears to be common practice that challenge organizers ask for the participants' feedback.
523 According to our survey three out of the four challenges (including Semantic Publishing Challenge) which
524 had more than one submission took into consideration the participants' feedback to adjust the tasks or to
525 define new tasks.

526 **Best Practice:** Exploiting participants feedback and involving them in the task definition creating a
527 direct link between different editions is a key success factor. The participants' early feedback can help to
528 identify practical needs and correspondingly shape and adjust tasks. Tasks proposed or emerged from the
529 community can be turned into an incentive to participate.

530 **3.1.4 Community traction**

531 **Lesson:** Although the challenge had been announced to be open to everyone from industry and
532 academia, the initial expected participants were from the Semantic Web community. However, the
533 submitted solutions include participants with completely different research focus areas, even without
534 any Semantic Web background. This changed our perception of the core communities in the challenge.
535 In future, one might therefore consider defining a task that crosses domains, e.g., using a dataset of
536 publications from the Biomedical domain.

537 **Validation:** Evaluating the scientific profiles of participants and the submitted solutions highlights the
538 diversity of professions. The participants of Task 2 are mainly active researchers in the fields of NLP
539 (Natural Language Processing), Text Mining, and Information Retrieval. Submissions to Task 1 are
540 mostly from the linked data and semantic publishing community, addressing various subjects of interest
541 such as User Modeling, Library Science, and Artificial Intelligence. This diversity of professions was
542 acknowledged while inviting the members of the challenge's program committee, and during the process
543 of assigning reviewers.

544 **Best Practice:** Defining independent tasks and using datasets related to other fields of study can build
545 a bridge across disciplines. The use case dataset contains data about computer science publications,
546 and the super-event of the Semantic Publishing Challenge series, the ESWC conference, is an A-ranked

547 conference but focused on a dedicated sub-field of computer science. This choice of subject potentially
548 restricts the target audience and the publicity of the challenge; however, with a slight shift of any of these,
549 it becomes possible to involve other research communities.

550 **3.2 Lessons learned from building training and evaluation datasets**

551 The training and output dataset definition is also crucial parts when organizing a challenge. In the
552 Semantic Publishing Challenge case, we experimented with maintaining the same training and output
553 dataset, as well as the same tasks, as in the case of Task 1, and with modifying the dataset but keeping
554 almost the same tasks, as in the case of Task 2 and 3. This way, we bridged the gap between building up
555 initial datasets and exploring possibilities for innovative semantic publishing. As mentioned in Section 2.2,
556 we refined both the datasets and their corresponding tasks over the years according to the participants’
557 and organizers’ feedback.

558 **3.2.1 Dataset continuity**

559 **Lesson:** We noticed benefits of not only continuing the same tasks but also using the same datasets
560 across multiple editions of the challenge. In Task 1 of each edition, in fact, we evolved training and
561 evaluation datasets based on the same data source over the three years. Participants were able to reuse
562 their existing tools and extend the previously-created knowledge-bases with limited effort. However, for
563 the other tasks, whose datasets were not equally stable, we had to rebuild the competition every year
564 without being able to exploit the past experience. Once solutions were submitted for Task 2 though and it
565 was repeated with the same dataset in 2016 as in 2015, the Semantic Publishing Challenge immediately
566 gained corresponding profit as for Task 1, as the majority of the submitted solutions were resubmitted.
567 Nevertheless, this did not happen with Task 3, which did not gain traction in the first place and changing
568 the training dataset and tasks did not coincide with submissions. Therefore, the “continuity” lesson is
569 equally applicable to tasks as well as to datasets.

570 **Validation:** Dataset continuity is not as persistent as task continuity for most challenges, but it still
571 occurs. To be more precise, most challenges in principle reuse the same datasets across different editions:
572 two of the four Semantic Web Evaluation challenges with multiple editions reused the same dataset, while
573 the other two did the same but for one of their editions only considered a different dataset of the same
574 nature though.

575 **Best Practice:** Same datasets should be continuously reused over the course of different editions.
576 Nevertheless, eventually substituting them by another dataset of the same nature where the same tasks
577 and tools are equally applicable does not harm the challenge.

578 **3.2.2 Single dataset for all tasks**

579 **Lesson:** Similarly, we observed that it is valuable to use the same dataset for multiple tasks. For
580 instance, in the Semantic Web Challenge case, completely different datasets were used for Task 1 and 2
581 for the first edition, but complementary datasets were used for the same tasks during the second and third
582 edition, while Task 3 considered the previous year’s output of Task 1.

583 The participants can extend their existing tools to compete for different tasks, with limited effort. This
584 also opens new perspectives for future collaboration: participants’ work could be extended and integrated
585 in a shared effort for producing useful data. It is also worth highlighting the importance of such uniformity
586 for the organizers. It reduces the time needed to prepare and validate data, as well as the risk of errors and
587 imperfections. Last but not least, it enables designing interconnected tasks and producing richer output.

588 **Validation:** All four Semantic Web Evaluation challenges with multiple editions used the same dataset
589 or subsets of it for all different tasks of the challenge.

590 **Best Practice:** It is clearly beneficial for the challenge to consider the same dataset for all tasks.

591 **3.2.3 Exhaustive output dataset description**

592 **Lesson:** An aspect that was underestimated in the first editions of the Semantic Publishing Challenge
593 was the training and output dataset description. While we completely listed all data sources, we did not
594 provide enough information on the expected output: we went into details for the most relevant and critical
595 examples, but we did not provide the exact expected output for all cases in the training dataset. Such
596 information should have instead been provided as it impacts directly the quality of the submissions and
597 helps participants to refine their tools.

598 **Validation:** Based on the survey results, the other Semantic Web Evaluation challenges seem to share
599 the same principle about the exhaustive description of the dataset. To be more precise, only one of the
600 Semantic Web Evaluation challenges does not provide detailed and exhaustive description of the expected
601 output.

602 **Best Practice:** Exhaustive and detailed description of both the training and evaluation dataset is required,
603 as it affects the submissions' quality and helps participants to refine their tools.

604 **3.3 Lessons learned from evaluating results**

605 All three editions of the Semantic Publishing Challenge shared the same evaluation procedure (see
606 Section 2.2 for details). However, it presented some weaknesses, especially in the first two editions, which
607 we subsequently addressed. Three lessons are derived from these issues which are explained below.

608 **3.3.1 Entire dataset evaluation**

609 **Lesson:** Even though we asked participants to run their tools on the entire evaluation dataset, we
610 considered only a subset for the final evaluation. The subset has been randomly selected from clusters
611 representing different cases, which participants were required to address. On the one hand, since the
612 subset was representative of these cases, we received a fair indication of each tool capabilities. On the
613 other hand, some submissions were penalized as their tool could have worked well on other values, which
614 were not taken into account for the evaluation. In the second edition, we tried to resolve this issue by
615 increasing the number of evaluation queries, without reaching the desired results though, but causing
616 instead some additional overhead to the participants. In the third edition, we reduced the number of
617 evaluation queries, but we radically increased their coverage to assure that the greatest part of the dataset
618 (or even the whole dataset) is covered.

619 **Validation:** Our lesson learned was validated by our survey in this case too. To be more precise, only
620 one of the Semantic Web Evaluation challenges does not take into consideration the entire dataset for the
621 evaluation.

622 **Best Practice:** The evaluation method should cover the entire evaluation dataset to be fair, to avoid bias
623 and to reinforce submissions to maintain a high quality across the entire dataset.

624 **3.3.2 Disjoint training and evaluation dataset**

625 **Lesson:** During the first two editions of the Semantic Publishing Challenge, the evaluation dataset was
626 a superset of the training one. This may have resulted in some over-training of the tools, and caused
627 imbalance in the evaluation, as certain tools performed very well for the training dataset but not for the
628 entire dataset. In an effort to avoid this, we made the training and evaluation datasets disjoint for the third
629 edition of the Semantic Publishing Challenge. It is more appropriate to use completely disjoint datasets,
630 as a solution to avoid over-trained tools.

631 **Validation:** Our lesson learned regarding disjoint training and evaluation datasets was validated by the
632 other challenge organizers. Only one of the Semantic Web Evaluation challenges considers an evaluation
633 dataset which is a subset of the training dataset. All the others consider disjoint training and evaluation
634 datasets.

635 **Best Practice:** The training and evaluation dataset should be disjoint to avoid over-trained tools.

636 **3.3.3 Available evaluation tool**

637 **Lesson:** The evaluation was totally transparent and all participants received detailed feedback about
638 their scores, together with links to the open source tool used for the final evaluation. However we were
639 able to release the evaluation tool only after the challenge for the last two editions. The evaluation tool
640 was not made available after the 2014 edition, it was only made available after the 2015 edition, while
641 it was made available by the end of the training for the 2016 edition. It is instead more meaningful to
642 make it available during the training phase, as we did for the challenge's third edition. Participants can
643 then refine their tool and improve the overall quality of their output. Moreover, such an approach reduces
644 the (negative) impact of output imperfections. Though the content under evaluation was normalized and
645 minor differences were not considered as errors, some imperfections were not expected and were not
646 handled in advance. Some participants, for instance, produced CSV files with columns in a different
647 order or with minor differences in the IRI structure. These all could have been avoided if participants

648 had received feedback during the training phase, with the evaluation tool available as a downloadable
649 stand-alone application or as a service.

650 **Validation:** Our lesson learned regarding when to make the evaluation tool available was also validated
651 by our survey. To be more precise, all the Semantic Web Evaluation challenges make the evaluation
652 available to the challenge participants. There is only one that does not, but only because there is no
653 evaluation tool.

654 **Best Practice:** The evaluation tool should be made available to the participants as early as possible
655 while the participants work with the training dataset and fine tune their approaches.

656 **3.4 Lessons learned from expected output use and synergies**

657 In all three editions of the Semantic Publishing Challenge, the potential use of the expected output was
658 clearly stated in the call, but not the output dataset license; it was up to the participants to decide it.
659 Moreover, the challenge was disseminated and supported thanks to synergies with other events. In this
660 section, we outline lessons learned regarding how the expected use of the challenge output and synergies
661 reflect on the challenge perspective, also on the participants and their submissions.

662 **3.4.1 Expected output use**

663 **Lesson:** The uppermost goal of the Semantic Publishing challenge was to obtain the best output dataset.
664 To achieve that, it is required to identify the best performing tool, namely the tool that actually produces
665 the best output dataset. This tool – or a refined version – is subsequently used to generate the RDF
666 representation of the whole CEUR-WS.org corpus.⁵⁴ The fact that the submitted tools are expected to be
667 reused becomes a critical issue: participants' submission should not only target the challenge, but they
668 should produce an output that is directly reusable. Therefore, it is in fact critical to state how the results of
669 the challenge will be eventually used, in order to encourage and motivate participants.

670 **Validation:** Three out of the other four Semantic Web Evaluation challenges do clearly mention the
671 expected output use, as the Semantic Publishing Challenge does too.

672 **Best Practice:** The expected output use and conditions should be explicitly specified in advance.

673 **3.4.2 License**

674 **Lesson:** The incentive to organize the Semantic Publishing Challenge was to reuse the output dataset.
675 Thus, having the permission to do so, which is specified through the dataset license, but also to reuse the
676 tool that produces this output to systematically generate the CEUR-WS dataset, is of crucial importance.
677 Particular attention should be given to the licensing of the output produced by the participants. We did not
678 explicitly say which license the submitted solutions should have: we just requested from participants to
679 use an open license on data (at least as permissive as the source of data) and we encouraged open-source
680 licenses on the tools (but not mandatory). Most of the participants did not declare which exact license
681 applies to their data. This is an obstacle for its reusability: especially when data come from heterogeneous
682 sources (paper full texts copyrighted by the individual authors, as well as metadata copyrighted by the
683 workshops' chairs) and are heterogeneous in content and format, as in the case of CEUR-WS.org, it is
684 very important to provide an explicit representation of the licensing information.

685 **Validation:** Like the Semantic Publishing Challenge, none of the other Semantic Web Evaluation
686 Challenges specified the tool or output dataset license. As a result, none of the submitted solutions
687 provided any licensing information, apart from one challenge where some of the submitted solutions
688 provided licensing information. Even though all Semantic Web Evaluation Challenges follow the same
689 practice of not specifying the output dataset potential license, it becomes obvious based on the results that
690 explicitly specifying it is important if the challenge output is desired to be reused.

691 **Best Practice:** The output dataset license should be explicitly requested to be provided for each one
692 of the submitted solutions. Moreover, participants should be advised to respectively specify their tools'
693 licensing information, to enable inference of their potential re-usability.

694 **3.4.3 Conflicts and synergies**

695 **Lesson:** Based on our experience from organizing three editions of the Semantic Publishing Challenge,
696 we realized that the dissemination should happen in a targeted way. To this extent, other events thematically

697 relevant to the challenge are considered important synergies that contribute in generating interest and
698 identifying potential participants: For instance, in the Semantic Publishing Challenge case the fact that the
699 SePublica 2014 workshop on semantic publishing was organized at ESWC 2014 reflected positively on
700 our challenge, since we had fruitful discussions with its participants. Moreover, the fact that results from
701 the first two editions of the Semantic Publishing Challenge were presented at the SAVE-SD workshop on
702 semantics, analytics, visualization and enhancement of scholarly data, which was co-located with WWW
703 2015, contributed to the challenge dissemination and in particular to an audience both thematically and
704 technologically relevant to the challenge. To the contrary, in 2015, we introduced a task on interlinking and
705 realized possible conflicts with other challenges, like OAEI (Ontology Alignment Evaluation Initiative),
706 which may have resulted in the lack of participation to Task 3 – even though Task 3 did not intend to
707 cover the specialized scope of OAEI, but rather put the interlinking task into the scope of a certain use
708 case that merely served in aligning the task’s output among each other and with other datasets in the LOD
709 Cloud. Therefore, we concluded that it is important not only to generate interest but also to identify and
710 avoid potential conflicts.

711 **Validation:** All Semantic Web Evaluation challenges collaborate with the ESWC conference, as they
712 are co-located with this event. Besides the main conference which drives the challenges, it appears that
713 most of them, and in particular the most long-standing ones, also collaborate with other events and, in
714 particular, with other workshops. For instance, the QALD challenge collaborates with the CLEF QA
715 track⁵⁵, and the challenge on Semantic Sentiment Analysis collaborates with the workshop on Semantic
716 Sentiment Analysis⁵⁶, which is also co-organized with the ESWC conference. Last, the OKE challenge
717 collaborates with the Linked Data for Information Extraction workshop (LD4IE)⁵⁷ which, in turn, is
718 co-located with the International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC)⁵⁸. According to our survey, none of
719 the other challenges experienced conflicts with further challenges.

720 **Best Practice:** Establish synergies with other events that are thematically and/or technologically relevant
721 to reinforce dissemination and to identify potential participants.

722 4 CHALLENGE SOLUTIONS ANALYSIS

723 In this section, we discuss observations from the participants’ solutions and derive corresponding conclu-
724 sions that can be used in the Linked Data publishing domain. We group the lessons into four categories:
725 tools, ontologies, data and evaluation process; even though there is some overlap between these aspects.

726 4.1 Lessons learned from the tools

727 Valuable indications can be derived by looking at the tools implemented by the participants. In particular,
728 we focus on the software used to address Tasks 1 and 2.

729 4.1.1 Primary Analysis.

730 **Observation:** The Semantic Publishing Challenge tasks could be addressed by both generic and ad-hoc
731 solutions, as well as different methodologies and approaches, nevertheless solutions tend to converge.

732 For Task 1, two out of four solutions primarily consisted of a tool developed specifically to this task,
733 whereas the other two solutions only required task-specific templates or rules to be used within their
734 otherwise generic implementations. In the latter case, Solution 1.2 abstracts the extraction rules from the
735 implementation, whereas Solution 1.4 keeps them inline with the implementation. Those two solutions are
736 generic enough to be adapted even to other domains. Even though solutions were methodologically differ-
737 ent, two main approaches for dealing with the HTML pages prevailed: (i) *structure/layout-based* (relying
738 on the HTML code/structure) and (ii) *linguistic-based*. Three out of the four tools relied on structured-
739 /layout-based approach and only one on a partially linguistic-based approach (Solution 1.3).

740 As far as Task 2 is concerned, there were different methodologies and approaches combined in
741 different ways. The overall picture is summarized in Table 4 and Table 5. The nature of the task influenced
742 the proposed solutions. In fact it was composed of two subtasks: (i) identifying the structural components
743 of the PDF papers and (ii) processing the extracted text. Thus, some solutions mainly focused on *structure-*
744 *based* analysis (five out of eight); others gave more relevance to the *linguistic-based* analysis (three out of
745 eight). Last, up to six used the *linguistic-based* analysis to complement their primary approach, while two
746 solutions also used formatting styles/rules to increase the quality of their output (*style-based* analysis).

747 We also observed that most solutions implemented a modular pipeline. In particular, the solutions
748 which followed a structure-based analysis had a workflow with a single pipeline, whereas linguistic-
749 based approaches required parallel pipelines to address different aspects of the solution and to increase
750 performance. It is also worth mentioning that two solutions over eight adopted an iterative approach.
751 One of them re-iterated the same analysis multiple times in order to refine the results (Solution 2.4); the
752 other one (Solution 2.8) adopted a layered approach, in which each iteration adds new information to the
753 previously-produced output.

754 **Conclusion:** The solutions were methodologically different among each other, and modular and hybrid
755 solutions prevailed compared to case-specific ones. This is important as case-specific solutions do not
756 extend beyond the scope of challenges, but generic ones do. It is interesting to note that both 2015
757 and 2016 best solutions for Task 2 relied primarily on structure analysis, whereas the most innovative
758 solutions focused on linguistic analysis. This might indicate that further research on linguistic approaches
759 might bring interesting results for optimizing the output of such tasks. A deep analysis of the structure,
760 in fact, made participants capture more information; on the other hand, these approaches were quite
761 straightforward and less innovative. It is interesting, though, to note here that the best performing tool
762 of 2016 grounded its structured-based approach on a prior linguistic analysis, whereas most solutions
763 grounded their linguistic analysis on a prior structure analysis. Thus, hybrid solutions are obviously
764 required but their execution order should not be taken for granted. It is also worth discussing the recall
765 score of the linguistic-based tools: these tools most probably suffer from noisy text extraction. In fact
766 the three solutions (Solution 2.2, Solution 2.3 and Solution 2.4) that mainly rely on linguistic analysis
767 achieved the lowest recall scores both in 2015 and 2016 editions, even though they showed significant
768 improvement in the latter edition.

769 Similarly, the tool that relied on a linguistic analysis for Task 1 showed significantly lower precision
770 and recall, compared to the other tools, indicating that linguistic-based solutions are not enough, if not
771 supported by a precise structure analysis. Even though the linguistic-based approach was considered
772 rather innovative way of dealing with Task 1, the evaluation showed that a linguistic-based analysis might
773 not be able to perform as good as a structure-based one.

774 **4.1.2 Methodologies: extraction, intermediate format and machine learning**

775 **Observation:** Diverse methodologies were employed by the participants to extract and analyse content.
776 There were no prevalent approaches, but some tendencies were observed.

777 For Task 1, three out of four solutions considered rules to extract data from the HTML pages; two of
778 them considered CSS to define the rules, while the other one, which relied on linguistic-based analysis,
779 considered JAPE; the latter solution was based on crawling. Last, all solutions used regular expressions at
780 some point of their workflow.

781 For Task 2, half of the solutions in 2015 but only two out of five in 2016 extracted the text from PDF
782 documents and turned it into plain text. To the contrary, two out of six solutions in 2015 and four out of
783 five in 2016 extracted the text from the PDF files but turned it into XML. There was only one solution
784 that used HTML as intermediate format. We noted that, both in 2015 and 2016, the best performing
785 solutions relied on a PDF-to-XML extraction. Moreover, one solution changed from PDF-to-text to
786 PDF-to-XML and indeed performed better in 2016, but we cannot associate with high certainty if this
787 was the determining factor. Besides extraction, as far as text analysis is concerned, five solutions in 2015
788 and four in 2016 relied on supervised Machine Learning. Only two solutions in 2015 and one in 2016
789 (the same as in 2015) additionally relied on unsupervised Machine Learning to address Task 2. Last, all
790 solutions employed heuristics and regular expressions. Five out of six solutions in 2015 employed Natural
791 Language Processing (NLP) and Named Entity Recognition (NER), and those that also participated in
792 2015 kept NLP/NER in their workflows in 2016.

793 **Conclusion:** Solutions based on supervised Machine Learning were awarded as the most innovative
794 both in 2015 and in 2016. Therefore, it seems that there is potential on experimenting with supervised
795 Machine Learning approaches to address such a task. Nevertheless, even though the best performing
796 solution in 2015 did use supervised Machine Learning, it is not the case for 2016 which makes us
797 conclude that fundamentally alternative solutions might show good results too. Overall, there is potential
798 for improvement and plenty alternative methodologies can be investigated. The intermediate format used
799 by each solution, on the other hand, had no relevant impact on the final results.

800 **4.1.3 Source tools**

801 **Observation:** The Semantic Publishing Challenge call did not prescribe (i) the implementation language,
802 (ii) their license (iii) whether the tools should reuse existing components or external services, and
803 (iv) whether the tools should be open-sourced or not. The participants were allowed to follow their
804 preferred approaches.

805 Three out of four, as shown in Table 3, and seven out of eight solutions of Task 2, as shown in Table 6,
806 primarily relied on Java-based implementations. In both cases, the remaining solution relied on Python.
807 Two out of eight solutions for Task 2 complemented their Java-based implementations with Python-based
808 parts. Moreover, as it is observed in Table 3, for Task 1, three out of four solutions relied on tools totally
809 open-sourced, while the fourth one, the one that addressed both Task 1 and Task 2, relied on a stack of
810 tools which are open-sourced, but the workflow used was not. This is also observed in most tools for
811 Task 2, as shown in Table 6 (six out of the eight solutions). MIT was the most popular license, with half
812 solutions for Task 1 using it and one out of eight solutions for Task 2, followed by AGPL-3.0, with two
813 out eight solutions for Task 2 using it.

814 Last, half of the solutions (two out of four for Task 1 and four out of eight for Task 2) incorporated
815 external services to accomplish the tasks. The one of the two solutions for Task 1 that used external
816 services was the one that participated both in Task 1 and Task 2. GATE, DBpedia, CrossRef API and
817 FreeCite are most used external services.

818 **Conclusion:** Open-sourced tools prevailed over closed-sourced ones. None of the participants used a
819 totally closed or proprietary software. Most of the them used an open license, and Java and Python based
820 implementations prevailed both for Task 1 and Task 2. The integration of external services was also a
821 valuable solution for the participants.

822 **4.2 Lessons learned from models and ontologies**

823 In this section, we discuss the different solutions with respect to the data model, the vocabularies and the
824 way they used them to annotate the data.

825 **4.2.1 Data model**

826 **Observation:** All Task 1 solutions tend to converge regarding the data model, identifying the same
827 core concepts: *Conference*, *Workshop*, *Proceedings*, *Papers*, and *Person*. A few solutions covered more
828 details, for instance, Solution 1.1 identified also the concepts of *Invited Papers* and *Proceedings Chair*,
829 while Solution 1.3 captured different types of sessions by identifying additionally the concepts of *Session*,
830 *Keynote Session*, *Invited Session* and *Poster Session*, as well as the concepts of *Organization* and *Topic*. In
831 particular for Task 1, Solution 1.4 domain modeling was inspired by the model used in Solution 1.1, with
832 some simplifications.

833 In contrast, the data models used for Task 2 were more heterogeneous. There are six high-level
834 concepts identified by all solutions: *identifier*, *type*, *title*, *authors*, *affiliation* and *country*. Other entities
835 were instead described in different ways and with different granularity. That happened, for instance, to
836 the entities *organization*, *funding agency* and *grant*. In certain cases they are identified as separate entities
837 and in other cases their details constitute part of other entities descriptions (and are expressed as data or
838 object properties). The coverage of the data models was also heterogeneous: for the 2016 edition, for
839 instance, not all solutions identify the *sections* and capture the notion of caption of *figures* and *tables*.

840 **Conclusion:** Based on the aforementioned, we observe a trend of converging in respect to the model
841 the CEUR-WS.org dataset should have according to the submitted solutions. Most solutions converge on
842 the main identified concepts in the data (*Conference*, *Workshop*, *Proceedings*, *Paper* and *Person*) and on
843 the CEUR-WS.org dataset's graph at least for Task 1, namely the publications' metadata. The way the
844 tasks and their corresponding queries are described contributes towards this direction.

845 **4.2.2 Vocabularies**

846 **Observation:** There is a wide range of vocabularies and ontologies that can be used to annotate scholarly
847 data. Most of the solutions preferred to (re)use almost the same existing ontologies and vocabularies as
848 summarized in Table 7. Six out of the twelve solutions for both Task 1 and 2 used the Semantic Web for
849 Research Communities (*swrc*) vocabulary⁵⁹, five used the Bibliographic Ontology (*bibo*) vocabulary⁶⁰
850 and three used the Semantic Web Conference (*swc*) vocabulary⁶¹. Moreover, six solutions used one or
851 more vocabularies of the Semantic Publishing and Referencing Ontologies⁶² (*SPAR*). In particular, five

852 solutions used the FRBR-aligned Bibliographic Ontology⁶³ (*FaBiO*) ontology, three the Publishing Roles
853 Ontology⁶⁴ (*PRO*), three the Document Components Ontology⁶⁵ (*DoCO*), two the Bibliographic Reference
854 Ontology⁶⁶ (*BiRO*), two the Funding, Research Administration and Projects Ontology⁶⁷ (*FRAPO*) and
855 one the Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records⁶⁸ (*FRBR*). Besides the domain-specific
856 vocabularies and ontologies, eight solutions used the Dublin Core⁶⁹ vocabulary (*dc* and *dcterms*), eight
857 the Friend of a Friend vocabulary⁷⁰ (*foaf*), five solutions used the DBpedia ontology⁷¹ (*dbo*), three the
858 VCard⁷² (*vcard*) and two the *event*⁷³ and *timeline*⁷⁴ ontologies and *schema.org*⁷⁵. Last, there were four
859 solutions that used their own custom vocabularies, most of them in combination with existing ones, but
860 only one used barely its custom vocabulary.

861 In contrast to Task 1 solutions, which all intuitively converged on using the same vocabularies and
862 ontologies, Task 2 solutions reuse a wider range and relatively different vocabularies and ontologies,
863 to annotate the same entities appearing in the same data which is extracted from PDF files. This is a
864 consequence of the rather diverge data model considered by different solutions. Interestingly, most Task 2
865 solutions use sub-ontologies of the *SPAR* ontologies family. Last, most solutions reuse the three most
866 popular vocabularies in the education field according to ?. The general purpose vocabularies – such as
867 FOAF – used by the participants are also listed high in the same ranking.

868 **Conclusion:** It is evident that the spirit of vocabulary reuse gains traction. However, it is interesting that
869 different solutions used the same ontologies to annotate the same data differently (see also Section 4.2.3).

870 4.2.3 Annotations

871 **Observation:** Even though all solutions used almost the same vocabularies, not all of them used the
872 same classes to annotate the same *entities*. As far as Task 1 is concerned, all solutions only converged
873 on annotating *Persons* using the *foaf:Person* class. For the other main concepts the situation was
874 heterogeneous, as reported in Table 9. A few of them also explicitly annotated *Persons* using the
875 *foaf:Agent* class, even though *foaf:Person* is a subclass of *foaf:Agent*. *foaf:Agent* was
876 also used by one of the solutions during the first edition, but it was replaced by the more explicit
877 *foaf:Person*. The *Conference* concept was well-captured by all solutions. It is interesting to
878 note that, at the first edition, most solutions used more generic vocabulary terms, e.g., *swrc:Event*,
879 *swc:Event* or *swc:OrganizedEvent* to annotate the data. However, in the 2015 edition, most
880 solutions preferred to use more explicit vocabulary terms for the same concept, e.g., *swrc:Conference*
881 and *bibo:Conference*, while they also maintained the more generic vocabulary terms for events.
882 The same occurred with the *Paper* concept. The 2014 edition datasets were annotated using more
883 generic vocabulary terms, e.g., *swrc:Publication* or even *foaf:Document*, whereas in 2015
884 more explicit terms were preferred, such as *swrc:InProceedings* or *bibo:Article*. In particular
885 *swrc:InProceedings* was adopted by three out of four solutions.

886 In contrast to Task 1 solutions, which focus on identifying and describing concrete *entities*, Task
887 2 solutions mainly focus on capturing their *properties*. This is also evident from the fact that Task
888 2 solutions rarely provide the entities' types, whereas Task 1 solutions always do, even though this
889 information could be inferred from the properties used. Moreover, Task 2 solutions generate much
890 fewer entities than Task 1 solutions. All Task 2 solutions use approximately the same number of
891 properties. It is interesting though to note that solutions that follow in principle the linguistic ap-
892 proach tend to use more predicates, which are more explicit and more descriptive too. Only one
893 of Task 2 solutions (Solution 2.7) has a significantly higher number of predicates compared to the
894 other solutions. This occurs because different URIs are used for the same relationships appearing in
895 different files to annotate the data. For instance, the *section-title* property appears with 37 different
896 URIs, such as the following: `<http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1558/paper5#section-title>`,
897 or `<http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1303/paper_4#section-title>`. However, such a choice
898 prevents easily identifying same relationships.

899 *DCMI* is the vocabulary most frequently used by all solutions for annotating the *identifier* and the
900 *title*. *RDF(S)* is also used for the *title* (represented as *rdfs:label*), as well as for the entities' *types*.
901 For the remaining properties, a wide range of different vocabularies are considered, but they do not
902 converge on their choices. Indicatively: one of the solutions considers *schema:mentions* to describe
903 a citation, whereas other solutions consider *bibo:cites* or *biro:references*. In the same context,
904 some solutions associate authors to papers with the *dcterms:creator* property, whereas others
905 consider *foaf:maker*. Last, some solutions indicate the affiliation using the *swrc:affiliation*

906 property, whereas others use the `pro:relatesToOrganization`, or the publication year using the
907 `swrc:year`, whereas others use the `fabio:hasPublicationYear`.

908 **Conclusion:** On the one hand, the more familiar the data publishers get with the data, the more explicit
909 they become with the annotations they use and the more they converge on the choices they make. On the
910 other hand, the way different solutions extract particular properties reflects on the final data model.

911 4.3 Lessons learned from submitted RDF datasets

912 In this section, we discuss the different solutions with respect to the RDF dataset they produce.

913 4.3.1 Successive submissions improvements

914 **Observation:** From the first edition to the second edition of the Semantic Publishing Challenge, we
915 noticed that the participants who re-submit their solutions had improved the overall dataset, not only
916 the parts useful to answer the queries. For instance, all three solutions of Task 1 which participated in
917 both the 2014 and the 2015 editions modified the way they represented their data, and this resulted in
918 corresponding improvements to the overall dataset.

919 Indicatively, as far as Task 1 is concerned, Solution 1.2 addressed a number of shortcomings the
920 previous tool's version had, in particular regarding data transformations, which might have influenced
921 their precision improvement. They also employed their mappings' quality assessment to verify the
922 schema is valid with respect to the reused vocabularies and ontologies. To address the same issue and
923 avoid inconsistencies in their dataset, Solution 1.1 preferred to align the different ontologies classes and
924 properties, e.g., aligning BIBO to SWRC ontologies as SWC already has some dependencies on SWRC.

925 As far as Task 2 is concerned, some parts of Solution 2.2, for instance, were changed for participating
926 in the 2016 edition. The authors employed different processing steps of their tool which were not used in
927 the previous edition, e.g., processing section headings, hierarchy and captions, but they also introduced
928 novel aspects driven by the challenge tasks and queries, e.g., extracting links from supplementary material.
929 Among the changes of Solution 2.4, it was the PDF extraction tool used, whose change might have
930 partially influenced their recall improvement, while a number of additional or new conditional heuristics
931 most probably influenced their precision improvement.

932 **Conclusion:** The improvement of the dataset was evident on some aspects and indeed the results were
933 more satisfying, but we still see that there is room for overall improvement. It is interesting though to
934 note that solutions did not remain focused on improving just the *data extraction* parts of the challenge,
935 but also the *data modeling*, even though the latter is not directly assessed by the challenge.

936 4.3.2 Dataset Structure

937 **Observation:** The different solutions differ significantly with respect to the size of the produced dataset.
938 This happens for different reasons. Solution 1.1 shows an extraordinary number of triples compared
939 to other solutions. This occurs to a certain extent because each concept is annotated with at least two
940 classes, making one fourth of the dataset to be type declarations. Moreover, they include even annotations
941 that indicate the type of the resource or property on a very low level, namely they use `rdfs:Class`,
942 `rdfs:Property`, as well as `owl:ObjectProperty` or `owl:AnnotationProperty` etc., which
943 counts for almost 2,000 triples of the total dataset. Solution 1.4 also shows a high number of triples.
944 This occurs because the same dataset contains triples describing the structure of the HTML page,
945 as well as triples describing the actual content of the pages. Nevertheless, the main reason that
946 causes the flow of triples is the fact that a new URI is generated each time a concept appears in
947 one of the CEUR-WS volumes. For instance, the person *Ruben Verborgh* appears to have 9 URIs,
948 e.g., the `<http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1034/#RubeniVerborgh>` for the Vol-1034 proceedings or
949 `<http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1184/#RubeniVerborgh>` for the Vol-1184 proceedings.
950 The person *Christoph Lange* appears to have 15 distinct URIs, e.g., for Vol-360 proceedings,
951 the `<http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-360/#ChristophiLange>`, or for Vol-1184 proceedings, the
952 `<http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-1184/#ChristophiLange>`.⁷⁶ Solutions 1.2 and 1.3 are approx-
953 imately at the same number of triples both for the 2014 and the 2015 editions.

954 **Conclusion:** There is a very high heterogeneity in the produced datasets; though solutions tend to agree
955 on used vocabularies, their design choices are very different and, as a consequence, the number and
956 organization of the triples is very heterogeneous.

957 **4.3.3 Coverage**

958 **Observation:** We further noticed that solutions rarely agree upon the extracted information. For instance,
959 they omit to extract certain information or extract wrong data. Overall, we observed significant differences
960 with respect to the number of identified entities per category. The results for Task 1 are summarized in
961 Table 10 and Table 9, while the results for Task 2 are summarized in Table 11.

962 Produced datasets were very heterogeneous in term of size, number of triples and entities. As far as
963 Task 1 is concerned, apparently, Solution 1.1 and Solution 1.3 used the individual pages to identify the
964 proceedings, whereas Solution 1.2 and Solution 1.4 used the index page to identify the proceedings, this is
965 the reason that there is so big difference in the number of *Proceedings* entities. The number of identified
966 papers is also significantly different among the different solutions, but in the *Persons* case we observe the
967 greatest variation in terms of numbers because of different practices of assigning URIs.

968 As far as Task 2 is concerned, due to the nature of the task – queries were quite heterogeneous, with a
969 clear distinction, for instance, between the analysis of the structural components and of the textual content
970 of the papers – solutions tend to omit certain subtasks and to optimize their performance on others. For
971 instance, in 2015, the best performing solution focused on precisely addressing the subtasks which were
972 related to the document structure and totally omitted queries related to funding and ontologies, as shown
973 in Table 5. Similarly, in 2016, certain solutions completely omitted the queries which were related to
974 supplementary material or tables and pictures captions. Consequently, the dataset size, as well as the
975 number of triples and entities significantly diverge among the solutions.

976 **Conclusion:** The datasets' heterogeneity is also evident in the amount and type of information each
977 dataset provides. However, the more the solutions improve, the more the solutions converge at least
978 regarding the number of retrieved and/or distinctly identified entities.

979 **4.4 Lessons learned from the solutions with respect to the evaluation**

980 In this section, we discuss the different solutions in respect to the dataset evaluation.

981 **4.4.1 Ranking**

982 **Observation:** For Task 1, in 2015 the performance ranking of the three tools evolved from 2014 has not
983 changed but their performance has improved except for Solution 1.1, which improved precision but recall
984 remain the same. Disregarding the two queries that were new in 2015, Solution 1.1, which had won the
985 best performance award in 2014, performs almost as well as Solution 1.4.

986 The trend was slightly different for Task 2: all tools participating to the Challenge for the second time
987 increased their performance, but the overall ranking changed. Solution 2.4 obtained a higher score than
988 Solution 2.2 in 2016, contrarily to what happened in 2015. The position of Solution 2.3 was stable.

989 **Conclusion:** Continuity helps participants to improve their tools; the overall ranking keeps stable if
990 the tasks (and queries) are kept stable; adjustments to the tasks (and queries) may impact the ranking,
991 favoring one team more than another.

992 **4.4.2 New and legacy solutions**

993 **Observation:** Task 1 participants both in 2014 and 2015 had an improved version of different aspects of
994 their solution, which resulted in correspondingly improved versions of the final dataset. The new Solution
995 1.4, which introduced a fundamentally new approach, achieved equally good results as the best solution
996 of 2014. The same trend was evident in Task 2, with a general improvement of all solutions that were
997 re-proposed for the second year (2015 and 2016).

998 **Conclusion:** Legacy solutions might be able to improve and bring stable and good results, however
999 there is still room for improvement and mainly for fundamentally new ideas that surpass problems that
1000 legacy solutions cannot deal with.

1001 **4.4.3 Equal chances**

1002 **Observation:** Solution 1.1, the winners of Task 1 in 2014, participated in 2015 with an improved
1003 version but did not win. The 2015 winner was a new tool with a brand new approach (Solution 1.4). The
1004 same happened for Task 2: in 2016, one winner (Solution 2.7) was a brand-new solution, the other one
1005 (Solution 2.2) was an extension and improvement of a legacy solution, but which did not win the year
1006 before.

1007 **Conclusion:** The winners were not the same in subsequent versions of the challenge: creativity won.

1008 **5 DISCUSSION ON SEMANTIC PUBLISHING CHALLENGE IMPACT FOR** 1009 **GENERATING HIGHER QUALITY LINKED DATA**

1010 In Section 1 we have motivated the Semantic Publishing Challenge as a means of producing high-quality
1011 Linked Data. For a comprehensive review of the state of the art regarding Linked Data quality assessment,
1012 we refer to the recent survey by ?. The Linked Data quality produced by the tools submitted has been
1013 assessed by comparing the output of a number of prescribed queries against our gold standard and
1014 measuring precision and recall, as explained in Section 2.2.4. Assessing the quality of Linked Data
1015 by running queries over it is a common approach, as their comparison of tools confirms. Therefore, a
1016 challenge designed as the Semantic Publishing Challenge could act as a means to assess the Linked Data
1017 quality and, and the better the results, the higher the Linked Data quality is expected to be.

1018 The specific quality metrics that our evaluation setup assesses can be connected to the general quality
1019 dimensions (accessibility, intrinsic, contextual and representational) and their corresponding metrics, as
1020 they are identified by ?. Moreover, few other quality dimensions' metrics which are not covered by the
1021 challenge's evaluation are assessed in the frame of this review. Note that some metrics are applicable for
1022 all tasks, whereas others are only for a certain task. In more details:

1023 **5.1 Accessibility dimensions**

1024 The accessibility dimensions involve aspects related to the access, authenticity and retrieval of the
1025 Linked Data (?). Our challenge required participants to make their data available, forcing this way
1026 the solutions to cover the availability dimension. Making the data available as an RDF dump was the
1027 minimum requirement set by the challenge, covering this way the accessibility of the RDF dumps metric.
1028 Participants were also encouraged to publish their data via other Triple Pattern Fragment (TPF) interfaces,
1029 such as SPARQL endpoints, but assessing its availability was not part of the challenge's evaluation.
1030 Moreover, participants were encouraged to publish their data using a certain license, without being a
1031 requirement though, boosting this way the licensing dimension (the corresponding detailed discussion is
1032 available at Section 3.4.2). While the aforementioned referred to all challenge's tasks, the interlinking
1033 dimension was only promoted by Task 3 which, after all, this is its actual goal.

1034 **5.2 Intrinsic dimensions**

1035 According to ?, the intrinsic dimensions focus on whether the information correctly, compactly and
1036 completely represents the real world and is logically consistent in itself. As the Semantic Publishing
1037 Challenge requires SPARQL queries to be executed against the Linked Data produced by the different
1038 solutions, the syntactic validity of the dataset is a prerequisite, boosting this way the metric for syntax
1039 error free documents and no malformed datatypes. While our challenge evaluation covers well the
1040 syntactic validity, the semantic accuracy is not evaluated. Nevertheless, the metric which is related to
1041 the properties misuse is discussed and assessed in a qualitative way in Section 4.2.3 of this paper, but
1042 it is not assessed quantitatively. Similarly, the population completeness, i.e., the percentage of real-
1043 world objects of a particular type that are represented in a dataset, is indirectly evaluated on the side.
1044 Namely, it is not thoroughly assessed if all real-world entities appear but to successfully answer the
1045 evaluation queries, the population completeness is prerequisite. Moreover, a comparative evaluation of
1046 the population completeness is performed in this work (see more detailed discussion at Section 4.3.3
1047 and Table 10, Table 11). Last, even though the solutions' dataset consistency dimension could have been
1048 evaluated and shed more light to their quality, it was not done by any of the challenge's series so far.

1049 **5.3 Contextual dimensions**

1050 The contextual dimensions highly depend on the context of the task at hand. In the case of relevancy
1051 dimension, the Semantic Publishing Challenge did not perform any relevant evaluation. Nevertheless,
1052 in this paper the coverage metric is addressed. To be more precise, in Section 4.3.3, the coverage is
1053 thoroughly discussed. However, the Semantic Publishing Challenge does contribute to the timeliness
1054 dimension. To be more precise, thanks to its continuity, it is assured that at least every year the challenge
1055 is organized, new dataset for the underlying CEUR-WS data is generated, boosting the freshness metric.

1056 **5.4 Representational dimension**

1057 The representational dimension captures aspects related to the data design (?). As far as the interoperability
1058 dimension is concerned, the Semantic Publishing Challenge promotes the reuse of existing terms and
1059 vocabularies and as shown in Table 7 and discussed in Section 4.2.3, the Semantic Publishing Challenge
1060 achieves its goal of promoting the re-use of existing vocabularies metric, albeit not evaluated automatically.
1061 Moreover, thanks to Task 3, the Semantic Publishing Challenge also promotes the re-use of existing terms.
1062 Even though it failed to attract participation, it is proven that such a task contributes into increasing the
1063 overall dataset quality.

1064 **6 CONCLUSIONS**

1065 One of the objectives of the Semantic Publishing Challenge is to produce Linked Data that contributes to
1066 improving scholarly communication. Nevertheless, the lessons learned from organizing this challenge are
1067 not only applicable in the case of a challenge on Semantic Publishing but in the case of other challenges
1068 too. Therefore, this work shed light not only on the three editions of this challenge organized by ourselves
1069 and distilled lessons learned from our experience, but we have also validated them against other challenges
1070 and concluded on general best practices for organizing such challenges. In a nutshell, continuity both
1071 in terms of the dataset and in terms of the tasks is important. Nevertheless, tasks should remain distinct,
1072 but they should refer to the same training and evaluation dataset, while participants' feedback should
1073 be taken into consideration to define or refine the tasks. Regarding the output, the larger the evaluation
1074 dataset is and the less overlapping with the training dataset, the best it is for verifying high coverage. The
1075 sooner the evaluation tool is made available, the better it is for the quality of the final output. Finally, it is
1076 a critical incentive for the participants to know how their output is intended to be reused.

1077 Besides the challenge's organizational aspects, we looked for evidence from the solutions proposed
1078 by the participants. Therefore, we analyzed them, reported our observations and came up with different
1079 conclusions related to Linked Data publishing practices followed by different participants. There are
1080 several positive aspects, among which the high participation and the quality of the produced results. This
1081 work allowed us to share those observations on semantifying scholarly data, using different ontological
1082 models, refining and extending existing datasets. Even though the Semantic Publishing Challenge focuses
1083 on scholarly data, the conclusions we draw based on our analysis are of interest for the entire community
1084 that publishes Linked Data. The possibility of sharing knowledge and solutions among participants was
1085 another key factor of the Semantic Publishing Challenge. In a nutshell, taking into consideration that most
1086 solutions relied on generic and open-sourced tools, which allows and enables their reuse for corresponding
1087 cases. Solutions, and thus the tools that produce them, have improved from one edition to the other.
1088 Even though different methodologies were followed, there are certain prevailing approaches – based on
1089 structure/layout or on linguistics – which were instantiated in different ways. Despite the fact that tools
1090 diverge, the produced data model and final annotations converge, as solutions become more mature from
1091 one edition to the other, while well-known vocabularies are reused.

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7 TABLES APPENDIX

Table 2. Semantic Publishing Challenge Evolution from 2014 to 2016

		2014 edition	2015 edition	2016 edition
Task 1	Task	Extracting data on workshops history and participants	Extracting data on workshops history and participants	Extracting data on workshops history and participants
	Source	CEUR-WS.org proceedings volumes	CEUR-WS.org proceedings volumes	CEUR-WS.org proceedings volumes
	Format	HTML and PDF	HTML	HTML
	Solutions	3	4	0
	Awards	best performance innovation	best performance innovation	–
	Decision	–	chairs' assessment	chairs' assessment
Task 2	Task	Extracting data on citations	Extracting data on citations, affiliations, funding	Extracting data on internal structure, affiliations, fundings
	Source	PubMed	CEUR-WS.org	CEUR-WS.org
	Format	XML	PDF	PDF
	Solutions	1	6	5
	Awards	–	best performance most innovative	best performance most innovative
	Decision	–	chairs' assessment	chairs' assessment
Task 3	Task	Open task: showcasing semantic publishing applications	Interlinking cross-dataset entities	Interlinking cross-dataset entities cross-task entities
	Source	–	CEUR-WS.org, Colinda DBLP, Springer LD Lancet, SWDF	CEUR-WS.org, Colinda DBLP, Springer LD
	Format	–	RDF	RDF
	Solutions	4	0	0
	Awards	most innovative (jury assessment)	–	–

Table 3. Task 1 solutions: their primary analysis methods, methodologies, implementations basis and evaluation results.

	Solution 1.1	Solution 1.2	Solution 1.3	Solution 1.4
Publications	?	?	?	?
	?	?	?	–
Primary analysis				
structure-based		✓	✓	
syntactic-based	✓			✓
linguistic-based			✓	
layout-based				✓
Methodology				
method	Crawling	Generic solution for abstracted mappings	Linguistic and structural analysis	Visual layout multi-aspect content analysis
case-specific	✓		✓ (partly)	✓ (partly)
template-based	✓	✓		
NLP/NER			✓	✓
Implementation				
basis	n/a	RML	GATE	FITLayout
language	Python	Java	Java	Java, HTML
rules language	XPath	RML, CSS	JAPE	HTML, CSS
code/rule separation		✓	✓	
regular expressions	✓	✓	✓	✓
external services			✓	✓
open source	✓	✓		✓
license	MIT ⁷⁷	MIT ⁷⁷	–	GPL-3.0
Evaluation				
precision improvement	11.1%	11.4%	10.7%	–
recall improvement	11.3%	11.3%	10.9%	–
best performing	✓ (2014)			✓ (2015)
most innovative			✓ (2014)	✓ (2015)

Table 4. Task 2 solutions: their primary analysis methods, their methodologies (i) in general as well as in respect to (ii) extraction, (iii) text recognition and (iv) use of machine learning techniques, and evaluation results.

	Solution 2.1	Solution 2.2	Solution 2.3	Solution 2.4	Solution 2.5	Solution 2.6	Solution 2.7	Solution 2.8
Publications	Tkaczyk (2015)	Klampfl (2016)	Nuzzolese (2016)	Sateli (2016)	Kovriguina (2015)	Ronzano (2015)	Ahmad (2016)	Ramesh (2016)
	–	Klampfl (2015)	Nuzzolese (2015)	Sateli (2015)	–	–	–	–
Primary Analysis								
structure-based	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
linguistic-based		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
presentation-based	✓				✓	✓		✓
Methodology								
workflow	parallel pipelines	parallel pipelines	single pipeline	iterative approach	single pipeline	single pipeline	single pipeline	layered approach
external services		✓	✓	✓		✓		
Extraction								
PDF-to-XML	✓	✓		✓ (2016)			✓	✓
PDF-to-HTML					✓			
PDF-to-text			✓	✓ (2015)		✓	✓	
Machine Learning								
supervised	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓
unsupervised	✓	✓						
CRF	✓	✓						✓
Text recognition								
NLP/NER		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
heuristics	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
regEx	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Evaluation								
best performing	✓ (2015)						✓ (2016)	
most innovative		✓ (2016)		✓ (2015)				

Table 5. Task 2 solutions: how they address different subtasks to accomplish Task 2. **n/a** stands for subtasks that were not required the year the solution participated to the challenge. **X** stands for subtasks that were not addressed by a certain solution.

Information to extract	Solution 2.1	Solution 2.2	Solution 2.3	Solution 2.4	Solution 2.5	Solution 2.6	Solution 2.7	Solution 2.8
document structure	enhanced docstrum	max entropy, merge & split, clustering	NLP to break the text down in sections & sentences	span between Gazetteer's segment headers	font characteristics, text position	rule-based iterative PDF analysis	heuristics on titles, capital-case and style	level I & II CRF
fragments' classification	SVM	supervised ML	Stanford CoreNLP & NLTK	Gazetteer	font-based blocks & sorting	structural features, chunk-& sentence-based SVM	pattern-matching	level II CRF
authors	SVM (LibSVM)	unsupervised ML & classification	heuristics, NER, CoreNLP	Gazetteer's person first names	e-mail 1st part frequent patterns & string comparison	layout info, ANNIE, external repos	from plain text: start/end identifiers return character	level III CRF
affiliations	CRF	unsupervised ML & classification	NER, statistical rules, patterns	organizations names rules patterns	e-mail 2nd part frequent patterns & string comparison	ANNIE, external repos	from plain text: start/end identifiers return character	level III CRF, affiliation markers, POS, NER
funding	X	NER, sequence classification	'Acknowledgments' section, regex, number or identifier	'Acknowledgments' section, upper-initial word token or name of organization	'Acknowledgments' section, string-matching: 'support/fundl sponsor', etc.	manual JAPE grammars	'Acknowledgments' section, string matching: 'the'... 'project', etc.	level II CRF
references	CRF	geometrical block segmentation	ParseCit CrossRef	hand-crafting rules for multiple cases	Heuristics on 'References' section	external services	n/a	level III CRF (even though n/a in 2016)
ontologies	X	n/a	match named entities to indexed ontologies	root tokens of ontology names	'Abstract' stop-list of acronyms	JAPE grammars	n/a	n/a
tables & figures	n/a	max entropy, merge & split	X	'Table' 'Figure Fig' trigger words	n/a	n/a	heuristics on captions, string matching	level II CRF
supplementary material	n/a	max entropy, merge & split	X	heuristics on links	n/a	n/a	heuristics on links and string matching	X

Table 6. Implementation details for Task 2 solutions

	Solution 2.1	Solution 2.2	Solution 2.3	Solution 2.4	Solution 2.5	Solution 2.6	Solution 2.7	Solution 2.8
Implementation language								
C++								✓
Java	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Python		✓	✓		✓			
PDF character extraction								
Apache PDFBox ⁷⁹		✓					✓	✓
iText ⁸⁰	✓							
Poppler ⁸¹						✓		
PDFMiner ⁸²			✓		✓			
PDFX ⁸³				✓ (2016)		✓	✓	
Xpdf ⁸⁴				✓ (2015)				
Intermediate representation								
HTML					✓			
JSON			✓					
text		✓		✓	✓		✓	
XML	✓ (NLM JATS)					✓	✓	✓ (NLM JATS)
External components								
CrossRef API ⁸⁵			✓			✓		
DBpedia Spotlight ⁸⁶				✓		✓		
GATE ⁸⁷		✓		✓		✓		
others	GRMM ⁹¹ , LibSVM ⁹² , Mallet ⁹³	crfsuite ⁹⁷ , OpenNLP ⁹⁸ , ParsCit ⁹⁹ ,	FRED ¹⁰⁶ , FreeCite ¹⁰⁷ , Stanford ¹⁰⁸ , CoreNLP, NLTK ¹⁰⁹ , (WordNet ¹¹⁰ , BabelNet ¹¹¹)	DBpedia SPARQL end-point	Grab spider ¹¹⁴ , BeautifulSoup ¹¹⁵	ANNIE ¹²⁰ , Bibsonomy ¹²¹ , FreeCite ¹²² , FundRef ¹²³	EDITpad ¹²⁵ Pro	Stanford ¹³⁰ , NERTagger, CRF++ ¹³¹ , CoNLL ¹³² , JATS2RDF ¹³³
(Open Source) License	AGPL-3.0 ¹³⁴	AGPL-3.0	not specified	LGPL-3.0 ¹³⁵	MIT ¹³⁶	not specified	not specified	not specified

Table 7. Task 1 and 2 solutions: the vocabularies used to annotate the data.

	Sol 1.1	Sol 1.2	Sol 1.3	Sol 1.4	Sol 2.1	Sol 2.2	Sol 2.3	Sol 2.4	Sol 2.5	Sol 2.6	Sol 2.7	Sol 2.8
bibo ¹³⁷	✓	✓		✓				✓	✓			
co			✓							✓		
DBpedia ¹³⁸	✓		✓	✓		✓			✓			
DC ¹³⁹	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓			✓
DCterms ¹⁴⁰	✓			✓	✓			✓		✓		
event ¹⁴¹		✓							✓			
FOAF ¹⁴²	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓		✓
geonames ¹⁴³												
schema ¹⁴⁴						✓		✓				
SKOS ¹⁴⁵	✓											
SPAR ¹⁴⁶		✓	✓				✓	✓		✓		✓
BiRO			✓							✓		
CI TO												✓
DoCO							✓	✓				✓
FaBiO		✓	✓				✓	✓		✓		
FRAPO							✓	✓				
FRBR			✓									
PRO			✓				✓	✓		✓		
SWC ¹⁴⁷	✓			✓				✓				
SWRC ¹⁴⁸	✓	✓	✓	✓					✓	✓		
timeline ¹⁴⁹	✓			✓								
vcard ¹⁵⁰			✓	✓	✓							
custom								✓	✓		✓	✓

Table 8. Statistics about the model (Task 1 – 2014 and 2015 editions)

year	Solution 1.1		Solution 1.2		Solution 1.3		Solution 1.4
	2014	2015	2014	2015	2014	2015	2015
Conferences	swc:OrganizedEvent	swc:OrganizedEvent	swc:Event	bibo:Conference	swrc:Event	swrc:Conference	swrc:ConferenceEvent
Workshops	bibo:Workshop	bibo:Workshop	swc:Event	bibo:Workshop	swrc:Event	swrc:Workshop	swrc:Section
Proceedings	swrc:Proceedings	bibo:Proceeding	bibo:Volume	bibo:Proceeding	swrc:Proceedings	swrc:Proceedings	swrc:Proceedings
Papers	swrc:InProceedings	swrc:InProceedings, foaf:Document	bibo:Article	swrc:InProceedings	swrc:Publication	swrc:Publication	swc:Paper
Persons	foaf:Agent	foaf:Person	foaf:Person	foaf:Person	foaf:Person	foaf:Person	foaf:Person

Table 9. Statistics about the number of entities per concept for each solution (Task 1 – 2014 and 2015 editions)

year	Solution 1.1		Solution 1.2		Solution 1.3		Solution 1.4
	2014	2015	2014	2015	2014	2015	2015
Conferences	21	46		46		5	47
Workshops	132	252	14	1,393	1,516	127	198
Proceedings	126	243	65	1,392	124	202	1,353
Papers	1,634	3,801	971	2,452	1,110	720	2,470
Persons	2,854	6,700	202	6,414	2,794	3,402	11,034

Table 10. Statistics about the produced dataset (Task 1 – 2014 and 2015 editions)

year	Solution 1.1		Solution 1.2		Solution 1.3		Solution 1.4
	2014	2015	2014	2015	2014	2015	2015
dataset size	1.5M	25M	1.7M	7.2M	2.7M	9.1M	9.7M
# triples	32,088	177,752	14,178	58,858	60,130	62,231	79,444
# entities	4,770	11,428	1,258	11,803	9,691	11,656	19,090
# properties	60	46	43	23	45	48	23
# classes	8	30	5	10	10	19	6

Table 11. Statistics about the produced dataset (Task 2 – 2015 and 2016 editions)

	Sol 2.1	Sol 2.2		Sol 2.3	Sol 2.4	Sol 2.5	Sol 2.6	Sol 2.7	Sol 2.8
year	2015	2015	2016	2016	2015	2015	2015	2016	2016
dataset size	2.6M	1.5M	285	184K	3.6M	2.4M	17M	152	235
# triples	21,681	10,730	2,143	1,628	15,242	12,375	98,961	1,126	1,816
# entities		1,300	334	257	3,249	2,978	19,487		
# properties	12	23	23	15	19	21	36	571	23

NOTES

1097

- 1098 ¹<http://challenge.semanticweb.org/>
- 1100 ²<http://linkedup-challenge.org/>
- 1101 ³<http://2014.eswc-conferences.org/semantic-publishing-challenge.html>
- 1102 ⁴<http://2015.eswc-conferences.org/important-dates/call-SemPub>
- 1103 ⁵<http://2016.eswc-conferences.org/assessing-quality-scientific-output-its-ecosystem>
- 1104 ⁶<http://2014.eswc-conferences.org/important-dates/call-challenges.html>
- 1105 ⁷<http://2015.eswc-conferences.org/call-challenges>
- 1106 ⁸<http://2016.eswc-conferences.org/call-challenges>
- 1107 ⁹<http://ontologymatching.org/>
- 1108 ¹⁰<http://oaei.ontologymatching.org/>
- 1109 ¹¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_World_Wide_Web_Conference
- 1110 ¹²Very Large Databases; see <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/VLDB>
- 1111 ¹³<http://challenge.semanticweb.org/>
- 1112 ¹⁴https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Semantic_Web_Conference
- 1113 ¹⁵<http://qald.sebastianwalter.org/>
- 1114 ¹⁶<https://dbpedia.org>
- 1115 ¹⁷Learning Analytics and Knowledge; see http://meco.l3s.uni-hannover.de:9080/wp2/?page_id=18
- 1116 ¹⁸Linking Data for Education; see <http://linkedup-project.eu/>
- 1117 ¹⁹<http://linkedup-project.eu/>
- 1118 ²⁰<http://linkedup-challenge.org/>
- 1119 ²¹<http://aimashup.org/>
- 1120 ²²<http://alt.qcri.org/semEval2016/>
- 1121 ²³<http://wing.comp.nus.edu.sg/cl-scisumm2016/>
- 1122 ²⁴<http://2014.eswc-conferences.org/important-dates/call-challenges.html>
- 1123 ²⁵<http://2015.eswc-conferences.org/call-challenges>
- 1124 ²⁶<http://2016.eswc-conferences.org/call-challenges>
- 1125 ²⁷<http://alt.qcri.org/semEval2015/task12/>
- 1126 ²⁸<http://alt.qcri.org/semEval2015/>
- 1127 ²⁹<https://github.com/diegoref/ESWC-CLSA>
- 1128 ³⁰<https://github.com/anuzzolese/oke-challenge-2016>
- 1129 ³¹<http://persistence.uni-leipzig.org/nlp2rdf/>
- 1130 ³²On a more pragmatic level, a further reason was that one of the challenge organizers, Christoph Lange, has been technical editor of CEUR-WS.org since 2013 and thus has (i) the mandate to advance this publication service technically, and (ii) a deep understanding of the data.
- 1131
- 1132
- 1133 ³³<http://ceur-ws.org/>
- 1134 ³⁴<http://jats.nlm.nih.gov/>
- 1135 ³⁵<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK47081/>
- 1136 ³⁶<https://github.com/ceurws/lod/blob/master/data/ceur-ws.ttl>
- 1137 ³⁷<http://www.colinda.org/>
- 1138 ³⁸<http://dblp.l3s.de/dblp++.php>
- 1139 ³⁹<http://www.semanticlancet.eu/>
- 1140 ⁴⁰<http://data.semanticweb.org/>
- 1141 ⁴¹<http://lod.springer.com/>
- 1142 ⁴²<http://rml.io/data/SPC2016/CEUR-WS/CEUR-WStask1.rdf.gz>
- 1143 ⁴³<http://rml.io/data/SPC2016/CEUR-WS/CEUR-WStask2.rdf.gz>
- 1144 ⁴⁴<http://rml.io>
- 1145 ⁴⁵<https://www.w3.org/TR/r2rml/>
- 1146 ⁴⁶<https://www.w3.org/TR/selectors/>
- 1147 ⁴⁷<https://github.com/RMLio/RML-Mapper>
- 1148 ⁴⁸<https://gate.ac.uk/>
- 1149 ⁴⁹<http://www.fit.vutbr.cz/~burgetr/FITLayout/>

1150 ⁵⁰<http://cermine.ceon.pl/>
1151 ⁵¹<http://wit.istc.cnr.it/stlab-tools/fred>
1152 ⁵²<http://www.semanticsoftware.info/lodexporter>
1153 ⁵³<https://github.com/angelobo/SemPubEvaluator>
1154 ⁵⁴The actual integration of the extraction tool into the CEUR-WS.org production workflow is still in progress but is expected to
1155 conclude in 2016.
1156 ⁵⁵<http://nlp.uned.es/clef-qa/>
1157 ⁵⁶<http://www.maurodragoni.com/research/opinionmining/events/>
1158 ⁵⁷<http://web.informatik.uni-mannheim.de/ld4ie2016/LD4IE2016/Overview.html>
1159 ⁵⁸<http://iswc2016.semanticweb.org/>
1160 ⁵⁹<http://swrc.ontoware.org/ontology#>
1161 ⁶⁰<http://purl.org/ontology/bibo/>
1162 ⁶¹<http://data.semanticweb.org/ns/swc/ontology#>
1163 ⁶²<http://www.sparontologies.net/>
1164 ⁶³<http://purl.org/spar/fabio/>
1165 ⁶⁴<http://purl.org/spar/pro/>
1166 ⁶⁵<http://purl.org/spar/doco/>
1167 ⁶⁶<http://purl.org/spar/ biro/>
1168 ⁶⁷<http://purl.org/cerif/frapo/>
1169 ⁶⁸<http://purl.org/spar/frbr/>
1170 ⁶⁹<http://dublincore.org/documents/dcmi-terms/>
1171 ⁷⁰<http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>
1172 ⁷¹<http://dbpedia.org/ontology/>
1173 ⁷²<http://www.w3.org/2006/vcard/ns#>
1174 ⁷³<http://purl.org/NET/c4dm/event.owl#>
1175 ⁷⁴<http://purl.org/NET/c4dm/timeline.owl#>
1176 ⁷⁵<http://schema.org>
1177 ⁷⁶The definition of Task 1 was not explicit with regard to whether different persons with the same name (within or across different
1178 workshops proceedings volumes) should be assumed to be the same person or not. Our current work towards the release of a
1179 consolidated CEUR-WS.org dataset shows that the far majority of same names refers to the same person, which is plausible as
1180 CEUR-WS.org focuses on the relatively small computer science community. However, a general solution would be wrong to simply
1181 assume that same names mean same persons, whereas a full disambiguation of names would require a lot of information to be taken
1182 into account beyond the proceedings' tables of content: the title pages of the PDF papers plus possibly external resources.
1183 ⁷⁷<http://opensource.org/licenses/mit-license.html>
1184 ⁷⁸<https://pdfbox.apache.org/>
1185 ⁷⁹<https://pdfbox.apache.org/>
1186 ⁸⁰<http://itextpdf.com/>
1187 ⁸¹<https://poppler.freedesktop.org/>
1188 ⁸²<http://www.unixuser.org/~euske/python/pdfminer/>
1189 ⁸³<http://cs.unibo.it/save-sd/2016/papers/html/pdfx.cs.man.ac.uk>
1190 ⁸⁴<http://www.foolabs.com/xpdf/>
1191 ⁸⁵<http://api.crossref.org/>
1192 ⁸⁶<http://spotlight.dbpedia.org/>
1193 ⁸⁷<https://gate.ac.uk/>
1194 ⁸⁸<http://mallet.cs.umass.edu/grmm/>
1195 ⁸⁹<https://www.csie.ntu.edu.tw/~cjlin/libsvm/>
1196 ⁹⁰<http://mallet.cs.umass.edu/>
1197 ⁹¹<http://mallet.cs.umass.edu/grmm/>
1198 ⁹²<https://www.csie.ntu.edu.tw/~cjlin/libsvm/>
1199 ⁹³<http://mallet.cs.umass.edu/>
1200 ⁹⁴<http://www.chokkan.org/software/crfsuite/>
1201 ⁹⁵<https://opennlp.apache.org/>
1202 ⁹⁶<http://wing.comp.nus.edu.sg/parsCit/>
1203 ⁹⁷<http://www.chokkan.org/software/crfsuite/>
1204 ⁹⁸<https://opennlp.apache.org/>
1205 ⁹⁹<http://wing.comp.nus.edu.sg/parsCit/>
1206 ¹⁰⁰<http://wit.istc.cnr.it/stlab-tools/fred>
1207 ¹⁰¹<http://freecite.library.brown.edu/>
1208 ¹⁰²<http://stanfordnlp.github.io/CoreNLP/>
1209 ¹⁰³<http://www.nltk.org/>
1210 ¹⁰⁴<https://wordnet.princeton.edu/>
1211 ¹⁰⁵<http://babelnet.org/>
1212 ¹⁰⁶<http://wit.istc.cnr.it/stlab-tools/fred>
1213 ¹⁰⁷<http://freecite.library.brown.edu/>
1214 ¹⁰⁸<http://stanfordnlp.github.io/CoreNLP/>
1215 ¹⁰⁹<http://www.nltk.org/>
1216 ¹¹⁰<https://wordnet.princeton.edu/>
1217 ¹¹¹<http://babelnet.org/>
1218 ¹¹²<http://grablib.org/>
1219 ¹¹³<http://www.crummy.com/software/BeautifulSoup/>

1220 114<http://grablib.org/>
1221 115<http://www.crummy.com/software/BeautifulSoup/>
1222 116<https://gate.ac.uk/sale/tao/splitch6.html>
1223 117<http://www.bibsonomy.org/help/doc/api.html>
1224 118<http://freecite.library.brown.edu/>
1225 119<http://www.crossref.org/fundingdata/>
1226 120<https://gate.ac.uk/sale/tao/splitch6.html>
1227 121<http://www.bibsonomy.org/help/doc/api.html>
1228 122<http://freecite.library.brown.edu/>
1229 123<http://www.crossref.org/fundingdata/>
1230 124<https://www.editpadpro.com/>
1231 125<https://www.editpadpro.com/>
1232 126<http://nlp.stanford.edu/software/CRF-NER.shtml>
1233 127<https://taku910.github.io/crfpp/>
1234 128<http://www.cnts.ua.ac.be/conll2000/chunking/>
1235 129<https://github.com/Klortho/eutils-org/wiki/JATS2RDF>
1236 130<http://nlp.stanford.edu/software/CRF-NER.shtml>
1237 131<https://taku910.github.io/crfpp/>
1238 132<http://www.cnts.ua.ac.be/conll2000/chunking/>
1239 133<https://github.com/Klortho/eutils-org/wiki/JATS2RDF>
1240 134<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/agpl-3.0.en.html>
1241 135<https://opensource.org/licenses/lgpl-3.0.html>
1242 136<http://opensource.org/licenses/mit-license.html>
1243 137<http://purl.org/ontology/bibo/>
1244 138<http://dbpedia.org/ontology/>
1245 139<http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/>
1246 140<http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
1247 141<http://purl.org/NET/c4dm/event.owl#>
1248 142<http://xmlns.com/foaf/>
1249 143<http://www.geonames.org/ontology#>
1250 144<http://schema.org/>
1251 145<http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>
1252 146<http://www.sparontologies.net/>
1253 147<http://data.semanticweb.org/ns/swc/ontology#>
1254 148<http://swrc.ontoware.org/ontology#>
1255 149<http://purl.org/NET/c4dm/timeline.owl#>
1256 150<http://www.w3.org/2006/vcard/ns#>

